

Deliverable 3.2
Assessment of national and local practices

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WP6	Evaluation	U. PORTO
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Structural barriers to achieving meaningful equality of participation and opportunity for young people persist. These may be compounded for those facing intersectional disadvantage i.e. where disadvantage attached to being a young person is combined with that based on background factors related to race, ethnicity, gender, sexuality or (dis)ability. Efforts to promote youth participation draw on evidence that good early engagement experiences are crucial to the willingness of people to get involved again, where positive participation improves internal efficacy (confidence in one's own understanding of political affairs) and external efficacy (confidence that participation will make a difference). However, it follows that if that experience of engagement is negative – if it feels non-inclusive, uncomfortable, unrecognised or pointless – then it can generate mistrust and cynicism and reduce the chance of future participation. It is thus essential that we understand, evaluate and improve the deliberative and participatory practices in which young people engage.

This report outlines the key findings of a five-country study of practices of young people's participation and deliberation taking place in national and local organisations, youth councils and schools. The study aimed to: i) identify and map existing practices and experiences; ii) assess to what extent intersectional inclusion is considered in these practices and how far marginalised and excluded youth are recognised and involved; and iii) understand the strengths and limitations of challenging systematic exclusion and power imbalances through youth participation and deliberation. Using a combination of inductively and deductively derived common criteria, available documentation (including audio-visual materials) in educational (n= 25) and organisational (n=50) settings was analysed and compared.

Overall, the study found that the context of implementation – in terms of both the culture and traditions of promoting youth inclusion and participation in different countries, as well as the types of organisations and schools selected – were crucial to understanding how participation is approached, documented and described. However, at a high level, we can summarise overall findings in relation to the three objectives of the study as follows.

Mapping existing practices

- The organisations, educational institutions and projects studied were concerned to ensure that young people's voice contributed to decision making and, in many cases, provided publicly available documentation demonstrating how this was implemented in practice.
- Where organisations and schools explicitly followed a good practice model of youth voice (e.g. the Lundy model), the language used to describe their processes and outcomes facilitated their demonstration of good practice.
- There is evidence that broader programmes by local or national authorities or third sector organisations, implemented across a number of schools played a positive role in stimulating youth participation in the education sector.

On recognition of intersectional exclusion

- There was evident awareness that structural disadvantage is intersectional and efforts were made to reach out to marginalised youth and to ensure equality of opportunity, for example,

through accessibility of participation spaces for those with additional needs (including using accessible language) and making spaces safe and comfortable for all.

- It remains difficult for organisations and schools to avoid 'self-selection' bias when opening participation to all. Moreover, the desk-based nature of this study confines our findings to how good practice in engaging with more marginalised groups of young people is communicated in official documentation rather than in practice.

On challenging systematic exclusion through youth participation and deliberation

- Organisations, and schools to a lesser extent, are aware of the importance of monitoring and feeding back to young people the impact of their participation. This practice is enhanced where organisations adopt formal models of youth voice or are directly linked into local or national policy making structures.
- Organisations use a wide range of innovative and creative ways of engaging and expressing young people's views. More formal bodies, such as youth or student councils, effectively employ classic forms of consensus-seeking discussion and deliberation approaches to include young people in decision making. This ensures some power is transferred to young people.
- However, especially in schools, the critical capacities of deliberation and intersectionality to challenge systemic or structural inequalities are deployed only exceptionally. Careful thought must be given to balancing the need for encouraging classic deliberative and consensus-seeking skills with embracing the transformative potential of intersectional critique.

The fuller findings outlined below will be used, in conjunction with a parallel study of such practices at European level, to identify good practice, recommend ways to strengthen and extend inclusion, and help overcome systemic exclusion of a broader range of young people from participation and deliberation.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The increasingly tangible ‘democratic deficit’ (Norris, 2011) experienced by citizens in democratic societies of the twenty-first century is accompanied by a generational shift in models of citizenship. ‘Dutiful citizenship’, centred on voting as a core democratic act, is giving way to a form of ‘self-actualizing citizenship’ focused on more personally defined acts which carry a greater, immediate meaning and sense of achievement (Bennett, 2008: 14). **Young people** are at the forefront of this shift in citizenship styles, which is also characterised by loose, networked activism reflecting personal values, taste and lifestyles rather than life-long affiliation with formal political parties or civil society organisations (see, e.g. Hustinx, 2010). This kind of participation often takes up global issues and causes – environmental, anti-racist, social justice, anti-violence – but is enacted locally, through intensive engagement in one-off concrete projects where young people can do things by themselves and on their own terms (Bang, 2005). Such actions often comprise informal, individualized everyday activities – such as recycling, donating, political discussion, online and expressive (through song, art, dance, writing etc.) forms of articulating views – that take place in the everyday spaces most relevant to young people such as schools, neighbourhoods, households and friendship groups (Harris et al., 2010). These ‘micro-territories of the local’ are particularly important to young people, since young people find themselves structurally **excluded** from the formal public sphere (not least through the electoral voting age) and are more physically confined to localities than adults (Harris and Wyn, 2009; Andersson et al., 2019). The **deliberative and participatory practices** in which young people engage in these ‘micro-territories of the local’ are both substantively and formatively central to the enactment of citizenship. Such **local networks, organisations, schools and councils** facilitate the political agency of young people while the everyday experience of debating and taking action in such personal, every day and social arenas, gives greater meaning to political and social issues (ibid.).

1.1 MAPPING THE FIELD

Policy concerns around low rates of formal political participation among youth means that much research to date has focused on what young people’s localised, informal and pre-political participation means for our understanding of ‘politics’, the ‘political’ and young people’s activism (see, inter alia: O’Toole, 2003; Harris et al., 2010; Harris and Wyn, 2009; Wood, 2014; Pilkington and Pollock, 2015; Pickard, 2019; Genova, 2021). There has been less consideration of how youth **intersects** with other structural factors (of race, ethnicity, gender, sexuality, class and (dis)ability) to **include or exclude young people from participation**. Indeed, experts in the field warn against taking commitments to increasing ‘diversity’ at face value; the youth voluntary and civic sector, like many other sectors of public life, may seek to represent itself as being inclusive in its encouragement of participation and engagement through rhetorical and ‘branding’ shifts towards inclusion and diversity but ‘experiences of discrimination based on age, gender, race, ethnicity and other protected characteristics are still rife, and structural barriers to achieving meaningful equality of participation and opportunity persist’ (Mejias and Banaji, 2020: 128). It is important to note here that ‘youth’ itself is a socially constructed category rooted in largely western understandings and models of ‘transition’ from childhood to adulthood with their

accompanying power structures that intersect with those of gender, race and heteronormativity (see also: Bergold-Caldwell et al., 2024). This is evident in how key tropes in the representation of youth (as 'troubled' or 'in trouble') are interwoven with gendered, classed and racialised discourses. Moreover, in a context where young people are often not yet considered 'full' citizens, the notion of diversity as applied to a youth active citizenship context takes on an additional meaning (Mejias and Banaji, 2020: 130).

Research in the field to date suggests that an intersectional approach evidences how **such intersections compound young people's exclusion** from our understanding of active 'citizens'. However, it also points to how they may **generate new patterns of participation** based on complex emergent social and political identities. For example, the research on the intersection of **race and ethnicity** and youth participation points to the need for awareness that citizenship status or migrant background (Sime and Behrens, 2023), stigmatisation or misrecognition (Pilkington and Acik, 2020) raise additional barriers to participation. At the same time, it reveals how such intersections generate 'new grammars of action' among ethnic minority youth (O'Toole and Gale, 2010) and may, in some contexts, constitute a resource to act and stimulate social change (Pilkington et al., 2021). In relation to **gender**, the picture is also complex, with political inequality between young men and young women being less marked than one might expect (Grasso and Smith, 2022) and gender impacting less on the level of participation and more on its type. Young men are more likely to participate in manifest, formal or expressive types of politics while young women are more likely to participate in civic action and informal or protest oriented activities (Albanesi et al., 2012; Pfanzelt and Spies, 2019). However, studies find that young women have less confidence in their knowledge and understanding of political issues (internal efficacy) (Dermody et al., 2010; Henn and Foard, 2014); the significance of this is returned to below. Moreover, as with ethnic minority groups, research suggests that additional barriers to inclusion in participation are accompanied by the development of emergent new modes of participation. Harris (2008: 481), for example, finds that young women use digital technologies (online DIY culture, blogs, social networking sites) to develop 'new directions in activism, the construction of new participatory communities, and the development of new kinds of public selves, while also telling us important things about the limits of the kinds of conventional citizen subject positions offered to young women at this time'. **Social class** continues to impact participation in both formal and informal, community and online political participation across Europe, meaning that young people's social background forms an obstacle for their involvement (Grasso and Giugni, 2022). However, there is some evidence that while social inequality in voting is higher among young people than the general population, in all other political activities, social inequality impacts less on participation of young people than the general population. Education, for example, has a much greater impact on youth participation than household income for almost all political activities (Sloam, 2013). In relation to **(dis)ability** and **neurodiversity**, substantial inequalities continue to exist in community participation for disabled young people compared with non-disabled peers (Carroll et al., 2018; Moesby-Jensen, 2021). However, among young people with mental health issues, chronic physical illness or caring responsibilities that constrained their participation, research suggests that online spaces have proved enabling - allowing such young people the opportunity to control when and how engagement took place and to realise project-based political

identities (Collin, 2009). This does not necessarily mean that online participation challenges key structural inequalities. Collin's study suggests that formal participation conducted in this way continues to fail to provide access to existing power and decision-making structures to the most disadvantaged group of young citizens and may actually exacerbate the gap between those who are perceived to be 'engaged' and those who are not (ibid.). Not dissimilarly, Moesby-Jensen (2021: 189) finds that the possibility of participating in decision-making processes for young people with autism spectrum disorder (even about crucial issues concerning their own lives) is limited because of lack of attention to their diagnosis-related impairments and challenges.

Across these intersections, the common factor is that intersectional exclusion is accompanied by low internal efficacy (i.e. lack of confidence in their understanding of political affairs) and external efficacy (that their participation will make a difference). Mason et al. (2011), for example, find that young people living in disadvantaged areas are dissuaded from civic action and volunteering not only by logistical barriers, but by their lack of self-efficacy and their belief that they cannot make a difference. This makes **education** extremely important in tackling intersectional disadvantage. This is, first, because those with higher level educational qualifications are significantly more confident in their own knowledge and understanding of politics (internal efficacy) and tend to feel voting and elections offer valuable means of representation (external efficacy) (Henn and Foard, 2014). Secondly, it is because schools and colleges play a key role in neutralising social disadvantage and fostering democratic engagement (Sloam 2013: 853). Since inequalities in participation cumulate and become entrenched over time, ensuring intersectional inclusion at these early stages of participatory experience offers the opportunity to reduce participatory inequality into the future. Moreover, such intersectional inclusion should not be solely based on school-based democratic participation (e.g. in school councils, mock elections and debating clubs), but should go beyond formal education and schooling to consider education in its broadest sense. This is crucial if we consider deliberation to be a learning process (Bergold-Caldwell et al., 2024) that represents a 'democratic pedagogy of counter-narration' (Gibson, 2020: 439; Ackerley, 2007: 48) and is capable of opening up spaces for young people to imagine 'the world as it could be' (Gibson, 2020: 442). Accordingly, critical pedagogy becomes key in tackling such intersectional disadvantage as it considers education to be an inherently political act capable of tackling oppressive tendencies (Mayo, 2015) and in which young people as 'knowing Subjects, achieve a deepening awareness of both the socio-cultural reality which shapes their lives and of their capacity to transform that reality where people are in and with the world' (Freire, 1972: 51).

In order to do this, no educational space should be left unexplored where young people are able to engage in deliberation, to be viewed as equals, and to share knowledge and collaborate. They must be 'Subjects' in their own learning: 'No pedagogy which is truly liberating can remain distant from the oppressed by treating them as unfortunates [...] The oppressed must be their own example in the struggle for their redemption' (Freire, 1970: 54). These educational and deliberative spaces are not always explicitly represented as such but could be implicit in how politics and democracy are approached within those spaces (through utilising games, for example). Although these could be considered to be 'depoliticised' activities, they could have long-term results in providing young people the opportunity to learn about politics, democracy and how to deliberate (Mirshak, 2020). Widening the

opportunities for young people to experience the benefits of participation, formally and informally, will be a key factor in young people's future intentions to participate (Lopes et al., 2009).

There is, it seems, a virtuous circle in which exposure to political discussion, civic engagement, deliberation and participation in decision-making processes increases both internal and external efficacy and generates a culture of participation (Mason et al., 2011; Prats and Meunier, 2021; Villaman, 2024). A major review of participatory practice commissioned by the UK Government's Civil Renewal Unit concluded that 'A positive history of participation seems the key determining factor in the willingness of people to get involved again' (Involve, 2005: 12). However, if that experience of engagement is negative – if engagement, for example, compounds rather than overcomes a sense of one's own lack of efficacy – then we might anticipate that such engagement reduces future participation. Bad participatory practice, the Involve (ibid.) report states 'creates mistrust, wastes people's time and money and [...] subsequent proposals for involvement are likely to be greeted with cynicism and suspicion'.

This warning that bad practice may be worse than no practice must be heeded. While promoting youth participation may be well intentioned, usually rooted in arguments that it meets young people's rights or empowers youth, it has also been criticised, from different political perspectives, as either acting, in practice, to control young people (preventing more radical empowerment) or that valorising young people's knowledge over adult, professional knowledge is either naïve or potentially damaging for young people in the long term (Farthing, 2012). We must also take into account that young people's trust in social influencers, who often also engage in simplified, political messaging poses a new challenge to how early political engagement is experienced by young people. While research on the impact of such influencers is still emergent, there is evidence that young people who follow influencers who mainly discuss political issues¹, gain in internal efficacy and participate more in politics over time (Harff and Schmuck, 2023: 157). However, while political information from influencers can provide an informal pathway to politics that young people otherwise have difficulty accessing, it may mobilize primarily short-term and cause-related political action while the tendency for influencers to position themselves as an alternative to traditional political communicators and to employ anti-mainstream narratives may have the consequence of reducing further trust in political institutions and encourage resort to simplified and populist political sources (ibid.: 157-161). This makes it essential that we understand **what deliberative and participatory practices are conducted in schools and youth organisations and how well they work to get youth voice heard**, if we want to ensure that young people's expression of voice in these spaces contributes to a virtuous circle of inclusion and impact rather than a vicious circle of exclusion and disempowerment.

1.2 OBJECTIVES AND OUTPUTS

Following the rationale set out above, WP3 maps and assesses existing practices of young people's participation and deliberation in educational and organisational settings. It undertakes two mapping exercises - at the EU level and at the national/local level - which are designed to facilitate our

¹ This is not the case for general exposure to influencers, however, which is associated with lower levels of offline and online political participation (Harff and Schmuck, 2023: 158).

understanding of how far, and in what ways, intersectional inclusion is evident in existing practices. The first involved the assessment of current practice at EU level (Task 3.2) and the second, the assessment of practice at national and local levels (Task 3.3). The findings are delivered in the form of four key outputs: three deliverable reports, which are used to generate a practical tool as the fourth output. The assessment of current practice at EU level was reported in D3.1, while the current D3.2 report details the findings of the assessment of practice at national and local levels. These two sets of findings will allow us to identify good practice, recommend ways to strengthen and extend inclusion, and help overcome systemic exclusion of a broader range of young people from participation and deliberation. To this end, the integrated findings will be published in a forthcoming report including policy and practice recommendations (D3.3, due February 2025) and feed into the development of guidelines for the Intersectional Deliberative and Participatory Practices (I-DPP) and Intersectional Participatory Action Research and Deliberation (I-PARD) toolkits, and the development of the Inclusivity Footprint Calculator (D3.4, due April 2025). The latter will be a practical tool for use by organisations and practitioners to assess their own attention to inclusivity.

2. STUDY DESIGN

The national and local level analysis undertaken for this report was conducted in five countries: Denmark, Finland, Italy, Portugal and the United Kingdom. Through this study, we aimed to:

- Identify and map existing practices and experiences related to youth participation and deliberation in schools and organisations in the five countries of study;
- Assess to what extent intersectional inclusion is considered in these practices and how far marginalised and excluded youth are recognised and involved in these practices;
- Understand the strengths and limitations of challenging systematic exclusion and power imbalances through youth participation and deliberation.

The study was concerned to map practices of inclusion whether or not they were referred to using the academic terminology embedded in the project's conceptual framework and we were conscious that terms such as 'participation' and 'deliberation' may not be distinguished in the documents analysed and terms such as 'intersectionality' may not be used at all. Researchers were thus encouraged to identify practices either using the terms as employed within the documents or to look for evidence of practices using the following, broad definitions:

- **Participation** = 'acts that can occur, either individually or collectively, that are intrinsically concerned with shaping the society that we want to live in' (Vromen, 2003: 82-3).
- **Deliberation** = 'open, inclusive, informed and consequential discussions on one or more issues' (Curato et al., 2021: 3).
- **Intersectionality** = 'an approach, an analytical tool, and a political project for understanding, analysing and transforming multiple, complex dimensions of power and inequality' (Bergold-Caldwell et al., 2024: 7).

While the aim of the study was to identify ‘experiences’ and ‘practices’ of ‘deliberation’ and ‘participation’, it was designed primarily as desk-based evidence gathering exercise. Researchers were asked to identify cases for study on the basis of available documents setting out policies or strategies for youth participation and deliberation rather than to seek evidence of how young people experience such participation through new empirical research. The understanding of these practices is hence limited to the documentation available and presents an inherently partial picture. Nonetheless, in order to identify cases, researchers engaged with national and local experts and organisations for advice and, in some cases, requested further materials from schools and organisations selected to supplement information available publicly (e.g. on organisational websites). Any such ‘expert interviews’ were treated as facilitatory and contextual; they were not used as the evidence for analysis themselves. Researchers were also guided by the template for document analysis to capture as much evidence as possible of concrete practices implemented and, if available, young people’s reflections on their experiences of participation.

2.1 CASE SELECTION

In each country, researchers selected documents setting out the protocols and policies around youth participation and deliberation of 5 schools and 10 community organisations or projects. Recognising the diverse contexts of study, significant flexibility was allowed for teams to identify appropriate cases for study and the kind of documents that were used for analysis. However, a number of fixed criteria had to be satisfied, including:

- The cases selected should be **youth-focused** i.e. the policies or projects chosen must be designed exclusively, or primarily for young people.
- They should be **considered good practice in the field** e.g. they are recognised by national or local institutions, they are evaluated and cited by professionals in the field or they use models that are considered ‘good practice’ in the national context. Where these were available, national or local repositories or portals of good practices should be used.
- The documents should be **publicly available** where possible and, if non-publicly available document is used (e.g. an updated version of a document requested from the organisation or school), consent for their use and citation by the organisation concerned must be recorded. However, flexibility was given as to what counts as a document e.g. if the practices of a school youth council were illustrated on a website through a diagram, visualisation, set of photos (or combination of these), these could be screenshotted and used as a document source. The form of document being used was recorded in the analysis template.
- In line with the overall objectives of the SINCRONY project, the cases selected should **focus on ‘disadvantaged’ or ‘rural’ areas** (as relevant to the country context) **and/or focus on youth inclusion or young people with experience of marginalisation.**
- They should be **current**, as in ongoing or recently completed (i.e. implemented within the last ten years).

An initial list of cases and respective documents was generated by each partner and discussed with the Task Leaders before analysis began. This led to a slight revision of the list in a number of cases to

ensure maximum comparability of cases across the consortium. It is evident that this is a purposive rather than random or representative selection of cases. The particular skew towards the focus on disadvantaged areas and marginalised groups stems from the overall SINCRONY project objectives. The project's particular interest in inclusion and intersectionality also means that case selections prioritised projects and organisations with a conscious focus on diversity and inclusivity of marginalised groups.

It is important to emphasise that the researchers have not subjected the programmes or practices delivered by the organisations or projects studied to independent evaluation in terms of their process, delivery or impact. 'Good practice' is employed here, therefore, to reflect that the organisation or school is recognised within a community of practice as delivering good practice. In each national context, researchers drew on relevant benchmarking institutions to identify good practice. For example, in the UK, the Lundy Community of Practice network served as a gateway to identifying a range of different organisations and local authorities as well as individual educational trusts with a commitment to promoting youth voice. In Italy, some cases were identified as 'good practices' by institutional regional government with an explicit mandate to promote citizen participation and financed by regional laws through competitive calls. Where possible, regional repositories (*Osservatorio Partecipazione*) were used to identify such cases and gather documentation. In Finland, cases were selected drawing on examples cited as good practice by the National Agency for Education, recognition through awards such as 'Youth Council of the Year' or National Innovation prizes. For all partners, cases were also selected because they were acknowledged as relevant good practices by key stakeholders and referenced on various websites and by organisations committed to promoting youth wellbeing, inclusion, and voice. In countries like Denmark where there were a plethora of organisations and schools with good practice, it was crucial to represent the different parts of the educational sector (e.g. afterschools² and vocational schools) as well as different types of youth organisations in the final selection. However, all partners also sought to ensure that no single source of benchmarking was used.

2.2 CRITERIA FOR ASSESSMENT

Establishing the criteria for assessing the documents was undertaken in several stages. Initially, Task Leaders conducted a bottom-up pilot coding of six cases (four organisations and two schools in the UK) and elicited key themes that emerged. In parallel, the Task Leaders for Task 3.2 (European level analysis), conducted a similar provisional analysis of 5 EU level cases. The researchers compared the two sets of inductively generated criteria considered to represent 'good practice' in facilitating young people's participation and deliberation generated from the provisional analysis at different levels and adjusted the two lists so that, although not identical, the two sets of criteria were broadly in line and could be integrated at a later stage.

² An afterschool (*efterskole*) in Denmark is a form of independent (i.e. fee-paying although government subsidised), residential school for young people between the age of 14 to 17 where students complete primary education (Grade 9 or 10).

An important stage of criteria development for the national and local level study was to match the criteria emerging from the pilot coding against extant literature. To this end, key youth participation models such as the Hart (1992) 'ladder of participation' and the Lundy Model of Child Participation (Lundy, 2007) were consulted. While both these models focus on the importance of moving from tokenism to genuine engagement of children and young people in decisions affecting them, the linear model of the Hart participation ladder has been criticised for hierarchising modes of engagement and setting youth-initiated engagement as a gold standard that is not always achievable, or even appropriate in some cases. The Lundy model, based on four interrelated dimensions of youth participation - space, voice, audience and influence - in contrast is viewed as a dynamic and practitioner-friendly way to inform, understand, develop policy and audit existing practices. These four dimensions might be summarised briefly as: **Space**: Children and young people must be given safe, inclusive opportunities to form and express their view; **Voice**: Children and young people must be facilitated to express their views. These views could be imparted orally, in writing or print, in the form of art, or through any other media of the children and young people's choice; **Audience**: The view must be listened to, to ensure young people at least have a 'right of audience' – a guaranteed opportunity to communicate views to an identifiable individual or body with the responsibility to listen; **Influence**: The view must be acted upon, as appropriate. Children and young people should be told what decision was made, how their views were regarded and the reasons why action has proceeded in that way. At this stage we also drew on the SINCRONY project's literature review conducted on Deliberative Democracy, Youth and Intersectionality in preparation for the drafting of D2.1 to ensure that key criteria in the wider academic and practice literature had not been missed.

Following discussion by all partners at the SINCRONY consortium meeting (March 2024), the Task Leaders developed an analysis template with a list of criteria and descriptions of how these might be manifest in the documents to be studied (see Table 1). Six main criteria were employed: inclusion; participation; deliberation; intersectionality; recognition; and influence). Within each category, sub-criteria were employed to ensure that elements of both process and outcome were captured as well as to allow distinctions between engagement and empowerment objectives of activities.

Table 1 Criteria for analysis

Criteria		As evidenced by...
1. 'Inclusion'	1.1 Recruitment	Are young people included through self-selection, open invitation or random sampling? Are efforts made to reach out to marginalised youth or those who would not put themselves forward? If representatives are (s)elected, who has the opportunity to (s)elect representatives?
	1.2 Accessibility	Is there equality of opportunity to be included? Are spaces of participation accessible for those with additional needs? Is plain language used? Is language interpretation available?
	1.3 Belonging	Does inclusion go beyond opportunity for participation? Are efforts made to ensure young people feel they 'belong' in the participatory space?

		Is the space provided comfortable, welcoming and safe for young people?
2. 'Participation'	2.1 Voice	Does young people's voice contribute to decision making? What forms does this take (e.g. are young people included in co-design, co-production or 'consultation')?
	2.2 Site	Does participation (or deliberation) take place in non-formal, everyday settings?
	2.3 Power	Is participation young person-led or young person-initiated? Are young people seen as <i>citizens</i> or <i>citizens-in-the-making/future citizens</i> ?
	2.4 Voluntary	Is participation always voluntary?
	2.5 Support	Is training and support provided to enable participation?
3. 'Deliberation'	3.1 Form	What forms of deliberation are employed? Does deliberation include embodied and emotional modes of expression (e.g. story telling)? Are digital technologies and social media employed to facilitate deliberation?
	3.2 Critique	Does deliberation go beyond consensus-seeking? Does it make visible and challenge structural power relations?
4. 'Intersectionality'	4.1 Awareness	Is there awareness of the heterogeneity of 'youth' and the intersectional nature of exclusion?
	4.2 Critique	Is there recognition of the critical nature of intersectionality i.e. the exposing of multiple, interwoven power structures as a transformative process (rather than a checklist for identity inclusion)? Are the limits of deliberation, without structural change, recognised?
	4.3 Value	Is the potential for improving democracy by attention to the contribution of more a broader and more diverse range of deliberants recognised?
5. 'Recognition'	5.1 Acknowledgement and respect	Is participation publicly acknowledged? Is young people's voice accorded respect?
	5.2 Reward	Is participation rewarded or remunerated?
	5.3 Agency	Is the agency of young people as political actors recognised? Are young people seen as role models for participation?
6. 'Influence'	6.1 Monitoring	Is there a system for monitoring and evidencing impact of young people's participation?
	6.2 Outcome	What concrete examples or case studies are there of how young people's voice is listened to?

This was accompanied by a simple coding system, allowing each national team of researchers to record whether the criterion was i) absent; ii) referenced but no evidence of how it was applied was evident; or iii) referenced and accompanied by evidence of how this criterion was implemented in practice (see Table 2).

Table 2 Coding scheme

Code	
-1	There is no evidence of this criterion being considered
0	Reference is made to the criterion but there is no evidence of how it is implemented in practice
+1	There is evidence of concern with this criterion and of how it is implemented in practice

It was agreed across the Consortium that this was a coding system designed to facilitate comparison across cases (and between EU and national/local level cases) rather than a 'scoring' system that would be used to evaluate the different organisations. Two further revisions of the criteria document were made, first following a period of consultation with partners prior to implementation and then in response to early implementation experience. A visualisation of each case as coded against these criteria is provided in the Appendix.

In addition to the completion of the analysis template against all the criteria set out in Table 1, partners also completed an additional table, providing details of the organisation, the rationale for selection including relevant contextual information and a list of the documents used for the analysis.

2.3 CROSS-CASE ANALYSIS

Notwithstanding the process of reviewing selection of cases described above, the different societal contexts of study inevitably meant that different kinds of organisations, schools and programmes were available for selection across the five countries. Here we provide a brief summary of these differences as this is important to interpreting the findings set out in Section 3.

The organisations selected mainly fell into 3 broad categories. The two largest categories were: non-profit community organisations, charities or social enterprises (16 cases); and youth voice projects or services delivered by, or directly funded by, local councils or municipal authorities (17 cases). All countries selected non-profit/charity organisations. All countries except Denmark had local authority youth participation projects included amongst their cases. This reflects the rather different environment of youth organisation in Denmark, where large, umbrella and national organisations were available for study. Indeed, such umbrella or national organisations constitute the third main category (8 cases). Half of these cases emanated from Denmark, although all countries except Portugal included at least one similar case. The remaining cases were projects linked to international organisations (such as Save the Children) or projects funded by European project funding.

The organisations and projects selected can also be distinguished by their core activities. Although these are not mutually exclusive, and the lines are somewhat blurred between them, the majority (27 organisations) were focused on raising youth voice and ensuring the input of young people to policy (at local or national level). The second largest category (12 cases) were more broadly directed towards encouraging and developing skills in political participation and deliberative democracy or leadership. Reflecting the particular focus of SINCRONY, some of these projects were directed specifically towards marginalised groups e.g. young people with a migrant background. Other organisations might be seen as mainly focused on sports or creative activities but having a strong youth voice orientation (6 cases)

or being national or umbrella organisations addressing particular groups of young people (mental health, LGBTQ+, disability, refugee or migrant background youth etc.) (5 cases).

The educational setting cases were mainly selected based on expert recommendations, or profile, as being examples of good practice (15 cases). A number were also included because they were educational settings where marginalised or disadvantaged young people were concentrated (3 cases). Innovative or youth voice-oriented school-based projects run by local or national authorities or external organisations were also selected only in Italy and Portugal (7 cases).

The range of documents and sources gathered for analysis was wide and varied. This included a range of formal documents such as mission and values statements, vision and participation or youth/student voice strategy or policy documents, theory of change models, as well as statutes and articles of association for student bodies/councils. Participation records or minutes of meetings where available in the public domain were also used in a few cases. In schools, policies on equality, diversity and inclusion, anti-bullying, mentorship and student leadership were studied. Development plans as well as evaluation reports, where available, were used alongside final reports of individual projects or annual reports of ongoing programmes. In some cases, publicly disseminated manifestos, policy papers, recommendations or agreements ('pacts') were used as well as manuals, guidelines, handbooks, campaign and resource packs and toolkits on various practices employed. We understood 'documents' to additionally include visual images, videos and podcasts, which provided illustrations and examples of the kinds of participatory activities employed. Where available, informational material in school newspapers and social media publicising, or reporting on, activities or events was drawn on. It is important to note that the latter were not systematically reviewed (a separate task in the SINCRONY project analysed social media representations); for the current report, these sources were used where they appeared on the websites or public profiles of the organisations or schools studied.

In most cases the documents used for this analysis were those available in the public domain. In some cases, organisations and schools were contacted to request any additional information on relevant projects and processes and are cited only if permission was granted by the relevant organisation to do so. Informal interviews and discussion with representatives of the organisations projects or schools were also used, with permission, in some cases. These discussions often took place at the start of the process, when cases were being selected.

As described above, each team analysed the documents gathered for each case, completing the template where they provided a code/score against each sub-criterion and substantiated that score with a summary rationale as well as evidence from the documents to support this rationale. Relevant quotations were translated from their original languages to English by each national team to support the analysis in relation to each sub-criterion. The cross-case analysis was undertaken by, first, collating and visualising the codes for each criterion and sub-criterion for each case and country in the form of radar diagrams. This allowed an overall picture of where cases were evidencing different elements of the (sub)criteria and the formulation of an initial understanding of patterns across countries and settings. This was followed by a detailed descriptive analysis of the cross-case findings for each sub-criterion. At the final stage of analysis, we returned to the three main objectives of the study (see Section 2) and

drew on the provisional descriptive analyses to: i) map existing practices and experiences of youth participation and deliberation in schools and organisations; ii) establish to what extent intersectional inclusion is considered in these practices and how far marginalised and excluded youth are recognised and involved in these practices; and iii) understand the strengths and limitations of challenging systematic exclusion and power imbalances through youth participation and deliberation.

The findings are set out in Section 3 below according to these three aims. It is important to reiterate that, in reading the findings, the numeric coding was designed not to evaluate or hierarchise the cases, but to understand differences both across countries and between organisations and schools. We used this coding to generate a crude overview of patterns in the demonstration of the different criteria across the two sites (schools vs. organisations) and between countries. We then sought to understand these differences in relation to the particular contexts or approaches underpinning the cases and ascertain what could be learned and might be transferred from one context to another. Thus, while reference is made to ‘strong’ and ‘weak’ demonstration of particular criteria in the findings section below, this does not constitute an evaluation of projects or programmes of youth voice. Rather, this terminology is used in order to facilitate the identification of potential absences, for example in relation to intersectional inclusion or critical deliberation, that can be fed back to participating organisations and schools and inform the development of the Inclusivity Footprint Calculator.

3. FINDINGS

The findings of the analysis are set out in relation to the three key aims set out in Section 2: to identify and map existing practices and experiences related to youth participation and deliberation in schools and organisations in the five countries of study; to assess to what extent intersectional inclusion is considered in these practices and how far marginalised and excluded youth are recognised and involved in these practices; and to understand the strengths and limitations of challenging systematic exclusion and power imbalances through youth participation and deliberation.

3.1 Mapping Youth Participation and Deliberation Practices

Youth ‘participation’ is a multi-faceted and multi-sited process whereby young people, as active citizens, take part in, express views on, and have decision-making power about issues that affect them (Farthing, 2021: 73). The majority of activities assessed in this study related to this criterion of assessment and a number of sub-criteria were employed in the analysis to help assess, *inter alia*, whether young people’s voice actually contributed to decision making (‘voice’), whether the participation was young person-led (‘power’), and whether sufficient training and support was provided in order to enable participation especially of marginalised groups of young people (‘support’). The practices were also analysed in relation to whether or not they included deliberative forms of participation (‘deliberation’) and whether the engagement of young people was appropriately acknowledged and valued (‘recognition’).

3.1.1 Voice

In terms of participation, the good practice of our selected community organisations and schools is reflected most consistently in recognising and facilitating ‘youth voice’ in their decision-making and governance. Across all participating countries, the majority of organisations, institutions and projects studied were both concerned to ensure that young people’s voice contributed to decision making and provided evidence as to how this was implemented in practice (see Figure 1 – criteria 2.1).

Figure 1: Overview of community organisations on measurement criteria³

Organisations performing positively on the criterion of **youth voice** forefront the role of young people in the work they do, stating, for example, that ‘children, young people and families are at the centre of all we do. We hear and act on their voices at every stage of our work, and their perspectives influence the decisions we make’ (AF, UK). In many cases, they set out the specific model of youth participation they employ, detailing the different forms, settings and structures in and through which participation takes place (IOP, IT). Such organisations not only consult with young people but provide evidence that projects and campaigns are co-designed and co-produced with them.

Central to good practice is the involvement of young people from the first stage of agenda setting and designing project through to the development of their ideas together with decision makers and the wider community (UYHN, PT). The importance of their involvement from conception through to implementation was noted by young participants themselves:

³ The scores recorded in Figures 1 and 2 are derived as simple, summative totals from all cases across all five participating countries in accordance with the criteria set out in Section 2.2 and detailed in Table 2. Figure 1 refers to all community organisation cases (n=50) while Figure 2 refers to all school cases (n=25).

'It's us young people who set the agenda and it's our ideas that become reality' (RC, UK).

'We came up with so many ideas and then we concretised them and worked on them, and then we turned them into reality' (AID, DK).

The most radical case of youth voice was identified in Denmark, where a physical territory had been given over to young people and its day-to-day decision-making body, the Island Council, comprised solely of young people (UD, DK).

Where **local or regional authorities** take the lead in delivering youth participation structures, there were many positive examples of how youth voice can directly impact local policy making. In Finland, where it is a requirement that municipalities have youth councils, proposals by youth councils were often implemented as part of the participatory budgeting arrangements and young people participated in co-designing and co-producing policies related to youth, as well as monitoring their implementation (KYC, FI; SYC, FI). Given the research evidence on the significance for generating a sense of efficacy among young people of seeing the outcome of participation (see Section 1), a particularly good practice was identified in one city council's practice of not only offering a channel for any young resident to submit an initiative but guaranteeing a response and publishing both submissions and responses on its youth website (HYI, FI). Other positive examples of local authority practices included providing details of the resources and toolkits used to ensure young people's voices are included in decisions and changes and documenting case studies showing how young people's voices have informed concrete policy and practice (SC, UK; ABC, IT; WC, UK; WVC, UK; YYP, PT; YZ, IT).

Community organisations and projects may also engage young people in municipal politics with the aim of ensuring young people's voices have a direct impact on local policy. A project in Denmark offered workshops where young people developed a list of recommendations, which was published and presented at a public hearing in the City Hall (WDD, DK) while another in Italy used workshops and events to bring young participants together to imagine an urban regeneration project through dialogue and theatre and to collectively design open and inclusive spaces (RS, IT). Digital platforms were used to provide tools and resources to help young people shape their ideas, submit proposals for changes in their community (or vote on others' proposals) and work with municipalities to ensure selected proposals were implemented (MP, PT; CM, PT). In one case, a virtual game was used to engage young people in a process designed to inform development of wellbeing services in the local area (LP, FI).

In the case of both local authorities and community organisations, youth participation is often seen as having a positive impact on ensuring policies and services meet the needs of their (young) users and are efficient (Farthing, 2012). Notwithstanding the good intention behind such participatory projects, good practice in this area must also recognise and reward young people's input (see Section 3.1.5) and deliver concrete changes as a result of the participation (Macauley et al., 2022: 220).

Where projects and cases were evaluated less positively, it was often because they were primarily educative in nature or focused on the delivery of skills and education around participation in democratic practice such as voting, debating and deliberative democracy, with little information provided about how participants' voices are heard in decision-making processes (CM, FI; YP, FI; DUC,

DK; PA, PT). While such projects are important in generating the internal efficacy that enables participation and are inclusive in that they often target groups whose confidence to participate might be anticipated to be low, it is not clear how young people’s voice is heard or how it concretely contributes to decision-making.

Analysing the promotion of youth voice among the **schools** selected for study, we identify a complex and more varied picture (see Figure 2 for overview). This stems from the different statutory basis of school councils – being mandatory in Finland⁴ and Italy⁵ while recommended but not compulsory in the other countries⁶ of study – and the different nature of objects of study e.g. whether the student council practices themselves were studied or projects in which the school or the school council engaged. From the small sample selected for study, it is difficult to draw conclusions from these differences, especially given the dependency of the study on available documentation rather than direct research with those participating in these bodies and projects. Thus, we focus here on outlining some of the manifest differences between cases whilst raising some issues that it might be interesting to study further (see Section 4).

Figure 2: Overview of schools on measurement criteria

⁴ According to Finland’s Basic Education Act, schools ‘must have a student council consisting of its students [...] The purpose of the student council is to promote cooperation among students, opportunities for influence and participation, and to enhance collaboration between students and the education provider.’

⁵ In Italy, by national law, Testo Unico DL 297/94, two representatives of each school are part of the provincial school council, established by law DPR 567/96.

⁶ In the UK responsibility for education is devolved to the constituent national parliaments/assemblies. School councils are a statutory duty in Wales (Wales Statutory Instruments (2005) No.3200 (W.236) Regulation 3) but not elsewhere in the UK. No schools in Wales were selected among the UK cases studied here.

In some schools, student democracy is presented as a key dimension of the student experience. One private Danish High School, for example, declares student democracy to be the educational foundation on which the school is built. This is implemented via a student assembly that has broad powers and mechanisms to influence all aspects of the school from budgets and curriculum to canteen food (FHS, DK). A similar case was found in Portugal, where the school describes itself as a distinct educational community with a structure of assemblies, plenaries, small groups and teams that allow students to reflect, design and implement projects to change things in their school (YR, PT). In such cases, much emphasis is placed on student assemblies, which include all students with powers to propose, and in some cases hold open votes on, policies (LA, IT; SA, PT).

Where schools' councils are part of a mandatory system, it may be that the documentation provided does not emphasise the role these bodies have in allowing young people to influence decision-making in the school as it is taken for granted. However, in a number of cases, documentation did point to innovative ways in which school councils were operated. In one school in Finland, for example, an experimental form of school council was described, which includes all students in deliberative decision-making at class level and allows them to co-design and consult on weekly teaching plans as well as addressing a wide range of school-related issues in the class council (LS, FI). A newly opened school in the UK had introduced a range of roles (not only student councillors but also 'pioneers' and 'student leaders') with the aim to 'ensure that all voices within the academy are heard' (CABV, UK). In Denmark there were also examples of the introduction of innovative structures to facilitate youth voice in the vocational education sector, which is not renowned for having strong student democracy (H&RS, DK), and across Preparatory Basic Education schools. In the latter case, one initiative (MST, DK) aims to develop student councils that serve the most marginalised young people through listening exercises on topics decided upon by the association workshop and the youth council which they are then responsible for acting upon.

Another example of good practice relates to schools that evidence not only their commitment to ensuring youth voice is heard within the school, but that young people's participation is extended to the wider community. This includes students being involved in a wide range of civic projects, sometimes co-produced with external bodies (TCLT, UK; FBHS, DK; BBMS, UK) and leading to direct changes to local authority policies (RSKC, FI). In one case, the school organised a student congress in which young people showcased activities they had engaged in using the Lundy model (Space, Voice, Audience & Influence) domains (TCLT, UK). Conversely, some cases also illustrate how local authorities or external third sector bodies can stimulate youth voice in educational institutions. In Italy, one municipality had employed a civic imagination method designed to include and involve citizens and support self-organisation in neighbourhood renewal (NSQ, IT) while organisations including Save the Children, also promote youth voice projects with individual schools to bring positive change in teaching innovation, refurbishing school spaces, strengthening relationships between peers and with adults and expanding collaborations between schools and the local area (CF, IT). In Portugal, interesting schemes promoting youth voice in schools are run at national and local levels involving young people co-designing and producing proposals for funding to improve their school environment (PBS, PT; SV@DGE, PT; SWV, PT).

3.1.2 Power

If projects of youth participation are to go beyond the socialisation of young people into participation in existing political institutions and serve primarily a controlling function, then it is crucial that we assess whether or not **power** is actually transferred to young people in the course of their participation. In this study, this was measured by considering whether young people were envisaged in participatory programmes as equal, autonomous citizens or treated as not yet fully formed ‘citizens-of-the-future’ (Wood, 2022). In addition to the discursive positioning of young people in the documents analysed, a concrete measure of this was whether the participation offered was young person-led or -initiated.

On this criterion, those cases – such as municipal youth councils or parliaments – where young people are (s)elected, given power to represent others and to formally influence decision making and policy, naturally perform strongly. Across the different Youth Council cases in Finland, for example, although the bodies themselves report to municipal councils or parliament, they are youth-led in terms of organising their activities⁷. Young Mayor (YM, PT), citizens’ assembly (WDD, DK) and a number of UK local authority youth parliaments were also constituted by youth-led processes (WC, UK; WVC, UK). That this was rooted in an understanding of young people as actual (rather than ‘becoming’) citizens, was demonstrated in the statement that participation can help children and young people ‘be seen as and valued as citizens’ (SC, UK) and the idea that ‘Children are active citizens of this city and can bring fresh ideas and perspectives to the fore’ (LCC, UK).

The youth-governed territory noted above in Denmark is effectively youth-led and very much promotes a ‘youth as citizens perspective’ while one UK community organisation insists on young people having ‘a clear voice and influence in our charity’ as being the best way to ensure that ‘Everything we do here [...] is youth-led’ (RC, UK). In a number of policy manifesto and proposal-based projects and platforms, young people are envisaged as fully formed citizens with the expertise to critically explore relevant socio-political issues and design proposals for change in their communities (MP, PT; DD, PT; CM, PT). Other cases studied point to numerous completed youth-led activities in which ‘Young people have designed, developed, and facilitated 24 youth-led campaigns and projects to help their peers form and express their voices in ways that work for them’ (PP, UK).

Where activities are delivered by experts albeit designed to improve participatory skills and opportunities and thus empower young people in the long run, they are evaluated less positively since young people are seen as needing to be trained to participate and, as such, viewed as *citizens-in-the-making* (GG, FI; CM, FI; TM, PT; YPP, PT; IOP, IT). However, a note of warning about how we evaluate projects is evident from the case of one Danish project which essentially sees young people as ‘citizens-in-the-making’ since it aims primarily to train vocational school students for democratic participation, whilst at the same time being peer-led (DUC, DK). This may suggest that, rather than counterposing notions of ‘becoming’ and ‘being’ citizens, we need a more complex, dynamic and situated notion of youth citizenship as lying at the intersection of youth becoming, being and doing, which recognises the

⁷ The exception here is one national level case, which is initiated and led by the parliament (YP, FI).

ambiguities and uncertainties of being young, yet recognises the potential this holds for opening up fresh possibilities (Wood, 2022: 8-9).

The same general pattern is found across **schools** although they perform at a slightly lower level than organisations on the criterion of ‘power’ (see Figures 1 and 2). The most radical democratic practice was identified in Denmark, where one school claimed to be ‘the only high school in Denmark with democracy led equally by students and teachers’ (FHS, DK). One UK school also has an unusually bold statement of their commitment to empowering young people, stating in the Student Voice Policy that ‘Voice. Is. Power.’ (NC, UK). Other school practices are found to be youth-led (H&RS, DK; FBHS, DK; SS, FI, SWV, PT) or both youth-initiated and youth-led (MST, DK; RSKC, FI; PBS, PT; YR, PT; SA, PT). Most schools, however, tend to have a range of activities that are partially youth-led but often supported or directed overall by teachers with the aim of developing young people to become active citizens. This ‘citizens-in-the-making’ approach is usually implied but might be illustrated by references to the objectives of participation strategies as being that ‘All students should *become* [our emphasis], responsible citizens who make a positive contribution to society’ (CABV, UK).

3.1.3 Support

Among the key principles of good practice in youth participation is that participation must always be voluntary and that training and support to enable participation should be provided. Providing ‘support’ is particularly important in ensuring equal opportunity to participate and, as such, provides the mechanism for enacting inclusion. In practice, however, it is quite difficult to evaluate, with these principles either being implicit rather than explicit or throwing up some challenges to the siloing of these criteria separately to the overall aims of youth participation.

For example, the formal representative bodies included in our sample of cases tend to be well supported, in terms of administrative support, training, access to meeting facilities etc. (SYC, FI; TYC, FI; YM, PT; WC, UK; WVC, UK) but may function in a way that facilitates the incorporation or institutionalisation of youth voice rather than empowerment of alternative approaches. The delicate balance to be found here is articulated by one Danish organisation, which details the close support given to project participants but reflects also that:

It is a very difficult and sensitive balance. How do we scaffold youth participation, while still giving voice to young people’s own perspectives? And how do we balance between supporting their endeavours, while also teaching them to stand’. (AID, DK)

Most of the community organisation cases studied detail the support, mentoring and training they provide to enable young people to participate in campaigns and projects that will lead change in service provision, communities and politics (GG, FI; DGIC, DK; RC, UK; BY, UK; ABC, IT; DD, PT; IOP, IT). In some cases, this includes providing specific access to tools and platforms to enable networking, cooperation and guidance on making proposals or preparing texts (TM, PT; MP, PT) or to one-to-one mentors (YB, DK).

In **schools**, it is usually teachers who support the school based participatory processes, although information on how teachers, school youth workers or mentors support participation activities is

provided in a minority of cases (SS, FI; FBHS, DK; NSQ, IT; H&RS, DK). In activities delivered by Save the Children in Italy, a toolkit provided to help adults support youth participation (CF, IT), while in Portugal, 'responsible teachers' are said to support participatory processes either within the school or in relation to external opportunities (SA, PT; YR, PT; SWV, PT; SV@DGE, PT; PBS, PT). Among UK schools only one (BBMS, UK) provides any evidence about training and support provided, although others note that they do provide staff with training and development (TCLT, UK).

A further conundrum about what constitutes good practice is raised by considering school participatory programmes transnationally is that where projects are part of the school or college curriculum, they are effectively compulsory (PS, FI; LS, FI; DUC, DK; FHS, DK). While, in principle this goes against the 'voluntary' principle of good practice and potentially undermines the empowerment of young people to make choices for themselves, making participation compulsory ensures it reaches those who do not have the cultural or other capital required to participate otherwise.

3.1.4 Deliberation

In sharp contrast to the evidence of participation, especially the facilitation of youth voice, the document analysis revealed relatively weak evidence of **deliberative engagement** in either community organisations or schools (see Figures 1 and 2, above). Two sub-criteria were used to assess deliberative engagement. The first – 'form' – sought to establish the breadth of types of deliberation young people were involved in, including whether these included embodied and emotional modes of expression (e.g. story telling) and/or digital technologies and social media. The second – 'critique' – sought to identify the depth of deliberative practice, specifically whether deliberative activities went beyond seeking consensus and aimed to expose structural power relations with the objective of empowering young people to challenge inequalities stemming from them. Here the first of those sub-criteria is discussed, while the latter is discussed in Section 3.3 as it speaks to the limitations of challenging systematic exclusion and power imbalances through youth participation and deliberation.

Among **organisations**, those in Denmark and Finland most consistently demonstrated deliberative practice. Many of the Finnish selected cases were of youth councils whose work was deliberative by nature (KYC, FI; SYC, FI; TYC, FI; YCV, FI; YCP, FI) while among local authorities delivering youth participation in the UK, members of the Youth Council are included on Scrutiny Panels and Boards providing an opportunity to deliberate and critique council policy and delivery (WVC, UK; LCC, UK; WC, UK). Danish organisations also refer to the centrality of deliberation in their youth council and youth communities work (AID, DK). Our understanding of deliberative practices included a range of creative forms of expression where they are employed to support young people communicating their experiences and providing a strong voice. We identified a number of cases where creative forms such as art, filmmaking, photography, music, social media (TT, DK; CM, FI; GG, FI) or digital skills (BY, UK; ID, IT) were employed to such effect. Organisations in Denmark emphasised the importance of using storytelling, rap and dance to express young people's experiences and perspectives and promote deliberative processes (AID, DK; RAP, DK, TT, DK) while others included tools designed to facilitate practices of 'listening to' and 'discussing' in their Participation Toolkits (SC, UK). Good practice was also identified in the inclusion in these tools of activities designed to help young people express what

matters to them through emotional modes of expression (SC, UK) and in campaigns that included drawing, stories and videos to help influence decision making (BN, UK). Some organisations might not explicitly engage in deliberative practice but include in their core objectives, the development of young people's abilities to listen, discuss (critical) ideas and thoughts and to turn that discussion into group decision-making (TM, PT).

The particular challenges for **schools** in facilitating deliberative practices that are critical of institutional power structures is discussed in Section 3.3. Here it is worth noting that, even in relation to 'form' of deliberation, although all the schools selected had some form of youth council to facilitate youth voice, there were few elaborations on the nature of deliberation in which those councils engaged. One Danish school described three different deliberative fora (FHS, DK), while a Portuguese experimental programme had a number of fora where deliberation processes took place to achieve change in the school and as experience democratic decision-making (YR, PT). One UK school describes its Student Council in a way that evidences the use of deliberation in how decisions are taken (BBMS, UK) while another employs 'pupil-written policies' to facilitate deliberation amongst the Student Leadership team and the student body more widely (TCLT, UK). Schools in Finland employ digital tools, e.g. to collect opinions from students (e.g. SS, FI) or to publicise and disseminate decisions made (e.g. PS, FI). Some activities involve collective decision taking based on informed deliberation (LS, FI) and some projects undertaken by students have included emotional forms of expression (e.g. RSKC, FI). In cases where schools are engaging in wider programmes initiated by education departments or agencies, they make proposals but the deliberation and decision making is left to 'experts' (SV@DGE, PT). In other schools, young people are involved in choosing representatives but no deliberative practices (SWV, PT).

3.1.5 Recognition

Previous participation – not only in terms of outcome but also its experience – is key to young people's future participation. Central to ensuring a positive experience is respect for participants (Involve, 2005: 12). In analysing good practice among our selected cases, therefore, we considered how participation is recognised and accorded **acknowledgment** and **respect**.

Recognition is crucial for participation as is articulated succinctly by one organisation:

Children and young people's participation in programmes, projects and activities is central to their rights as a child to have their voice heard, listened to and acted upon. They also need to feel valued and respected to know that their contribution is appreciated and encourage them to continue participating (PP, UK).

Local authorities delivering participation programmes as well as national charities and community **organisations** were the most likely to explicitly include reference to the importance of recognition in their youth participation and voice strategy documents. This was particularly evident in the UK and Italy (AF, UK; YFNW, UK; RC, UK; PP, UK; WVC, UK; SC, UK; WC, UK; LCC, UK; SN, IT; X-C, IT; YZ, IT; IPGI, IT; ID, IT): Such recognition involves including young people in designing how they want their contribution to be recognised:

There should be procedures put in place, for recognising the involvement of children and young people and the valuable contribution they have made before a programme or activity starts. Don't forget to involve young people in designing their incentive, reward and recognition too! (PP, UK).

Organisations note the importance of making the acknowledgment of participation 'public' (WC, UK) and that young people's contributions are 'afforded the same level of respect as those contributions made by professionals' (LCC, UK). Recognition includes taking account of the particular qualities and skills that young people bring:

It is essential to recognise their [young people's] initiative, their efforts and to understand how indispensable they are to the society in which we live: [they bring] resources of empathy, sensitivity, taking a stand and supporting those in need in moments of extreme difficulty (YZ, IT).

Acknowledgment and respect are demonstrated through giving young people feedback so they know how their contributions and suggestions were implemented successfully (PP, UK; WVC, UK; SC, UK), and when they have not been implemented and the reasons behind this (KYC, FI; HYI, FI). Respect thus includes being open and honest with young people about the limits of potential outcomes of their participation:

Children and young people's involvement should be valued. They should be treated honestly. This means that their expectations are managed, and they are helped to understand any practical, legal or political boundaries of their involvement (WVC, UK).

Media coverage documenting projects and initiatives that feature young people was provided by many community organisations (DFUU, DK; UBN, PT; YP, FI) as well as through videos and pictures posted on community organisations' websites and social media accounts (AOYH, DK; DFUU, DK; CL, IT; WVC, UK; SYC, FI). According to one Finnish organisation, through showcasing videos that document young people's actions and contributions, they are able to:

gain immediate, visible, and tangible experiences of their strengths, participation, and societal impact, focusing on skills such as solution orientation, resilience, and teamwork, crucial for tackling today's significant challenges (GG, FI).

Recognition was also accorded by providing young people with artistic and creative platforms to perform and exhibit their contributions and experiences. In Denmark, for example, a writing programme had led to the publication and distribution of books by young participants followed by invitations for them to participate in podcasts and public debates and to give public readings of their work (YB, DK). In other community organisations, young people's contributions are acknowledged through being able to perform and exhibit their art and other creative productions in festivals and exhibitions (TT, DK; RAP, DK; UBN, PT; UYHN, PT), through radio productions (RS, IT), and through engaging in public debates (DFUU, DK; DUC, DK). Another form of 'practical recognition' was evidence of the contribution of young people to policy reports and policy recommendations (WDD, DK) or through submitting successful proposals to local and national policymakers (MP, PT; VYP, PT; DD, PT; YPP, PT).

In **schools**, young people's participation was also acknowledged and recognised through being featured and showcased on school websites and videos (FBHS, DK; H&RS, DK; MST, DK; EE, DK; SSOL, IT; TCLT, UK; BBMS, UK; YR, PT). In the case of one school, individual students involved in a recycling project were named as a way of giving them ownership of their contributions (PP, IT). 'Practical recognition' was also demonstrated in some selected schools where students' participation was respected and acknowledged by implementing their ideas and suggestions within the schools (PBS, PT; SA, PT) and forwarding their suggestions and proposals to educational authorities with the remit to implement change (SV@DGE, PT). The importance of implementation of their ideas for the whole school culture is captured by one student participating in a project giving voice to students in a school in Portugal:

In the past, we didn't even remember to participate because we weren't given that opportunity. When I arrived here [...] I saw many wrong things, and since they started this project, the school has been very different, even in terms of student relationships and behaviour. There is more respect for each other. (YR, PT)

Finally, students can be acknowledged and respected through award ceremonies and annual events where 'The work done by the youth is made visible [...] and the work done is remembered and the activities evaluated' (SS, FI). Moreover, senior leadership figures, including School Principals (LA, IT; AS, FI) and Former Presidents and Ministers of Education (RSKC, FI), can play a significant role in recognising and acknowledging students' participation.

For both organisations and schools, however, recognition was rarely accompanied by direct **reward** for participation. A small number of selected community organisations, predominantly in the UK, had reward and remuneration included in their policies and participation strategies. For example, one organisation states, 'At [PP, UK], we think children and young people should be paid when asked to undertake a task beyond the expectation of a volunteer role', and says that it pays 'Young Consultants' at subject area experts' rates (PP, UK). Another recognises the time and expertise of participants through employment contracts and cash or voucher payments or sometimes by gifts that include meals out, tickets for events, group leisure activities, and access to developmental activities (AF, UK). In Finland, participation in the Youth Councils is also rewarded (SYC, FI; TYCI, FI; YCP, FI). However, in most organisation cases, remuneration was replaced by reward through participation certificates (IOP, IT), feedback about outcome (MP, PT; VYP, PT) or through opportunities to gain accredited training or 'develop important and useful skills' (SC, UK; LCC, UK). In schools, there were even fewer cases of direct reference to rewarding or remunerating students for participation. One exception was a UK school, which utilised its House System to award students 'points' for their participation in activities as part of what it calls 'a comprehensive rewards system' (BBMS, UK). Other examples include awarding successful proposals a budget for implementation (PBS, PT; SWV, PT), offering awards and certificates (SV@DGE, PT), small snacks (SS, FI), and being part of the students' final evaluation process (SA, PT).

Finally, returning to the issue raised under 'power' – on what terms was young people's participation undertaken - we analysed the documentation for selected cases in terms of whether the recognition

they were afforded was as full, agent-ful citizens, who were role models for participation, or as objects of education, training and moulding to take up 'future' roles as citizens. On this sub-criterion, our selected community organisations performed well, with many explicitly recognising the agency of young people as political actors (or playing a crucial role in participatory and democratic processes) in their documents and practices (YB, DK; DFUU, DK; DUC, DK; UD, DK; AID, DK; TM, PT; MP, PT; UYHN, PT; VYP, PT; YM, PT; CM, PT; SN, IT; X-C, IT; IPGI, IT; YZ, IT; IOP, IT; ID, IT; BY, UK; WVC, UK). This is most powerfully illustrated by the case studied in Denmark of a physical territory that was effectively run by young people themselves through its Council comprised solely of young people (UD, DK). However, it is also eloquently articulated by members of a policy-oriented platform initiated by a group of young people themselves in Portugal:

We dream of a country that makes us want to grow and be part of the solution. A Portugal of opportunities, which calls for a new generation of leaders. We have the ambition, qualifications, talent, desire and responsibility to do our part: we have a voice in the matter [...] Let us take risks, let us fail. Above all, let us try. [...] we have a vision, an opinion, and we want to be part of the solution (CM, PT).

But additionally clear in local authority approaches in these examples from the UK and Portugal:

Children are active citizens of this city and can bring fresh ideas and perspectives to the fore (LCC, UK).

Through the course of the academic year, students deepen their knowledge on a topic of their choice and jointly develop proposals that aim to improve/innovate local public policies. Proposals are presented to members of the municipal executive and other stakeholders in a formal space – a forum. The strategic objective of the Project is to encourage active citizenship in young people, representative and participatory democracy, incorporate the perspective of young people in municipal policies and reinforce transversal skills (VYP, PT).

The agency of young people as political actors was also demonstrated through creative and artistic forms through taking part in festivals (RAP, DK) and through their ability to engage in various Youth Council roles (SYC, FI; TYCI, FI; YCV, FI; YCP, FI). In one case, a regional youth council had developed out of a youth initiative, when the local authority recognised the important contribution the young people were making and commissioned a community organisation to facilitate the institutionalisation of young people as political actors in a shadow youth authority (YFNW, UK). Demonstrating young people's political agency could also take place through engaging in educational dialogues with adults leading to the realisation that:

it is precisely young people and adolescents who are the most suitable and experienced people to talk about themselves and what makes them feel good and that, above all, they have the strength, motivation and skills to take charge of health promotion and community work initiatives themselves, with the right resources and legitimacy (CL, IT).

Similarly, a project in the UK started from the position that 'Young people are experts and agents of change: Young people's experience, perspectives, opinions and aspirations must be at the core of efforts to improve their safety' (RC, UK). This led to the production of a report setting out a youth-centred approach to violence, crime and public safety. This not only demonstrates the political agency of young working-class people, but that they are the experts that must be listened to by the 'adults'.

Young people were explicitly viewed as role models of participation in various community organisations (AOYH, DK; DGIC, DK; YZ, IT; IPGI, IT; PP, UK; WVC, UK; LCC, UK). A clear example of this was an Italian project focusing on engaging young people with a migrant background, which sets out its aim as:

To encourage 'the dream', to give political and civic space and centrality to young people with a migrant background, facilitating meeting and engaging in dialogue with administrators, allowing them to imagine paths in politics, in civic commitment, working to integrate young Italians with a migrant background and new generations in projects, associations, volunteer programmes. So that they can be visible and serve as a model for more recently arrived young people who are confronted with important identity and cultural issues (IOP, IT).

The agency of young people as political actors was recognised by a number of **schools**, predominantly in Denmark, through their websites and social media pages (including featured videos) and annual reports (FBHS, DK; H&RS, DK; MST, DK; FHS, DK; SA, PT; AS, FI). It was particularly emphasised by one UK school, which states that it understands:

learning to mean growing in knowledge, self-reliance and in responsibility towards others. Achieving this will allow pupils and staff to develop a sense of agency and co-agency, which is the awareness that we are powerful and can affect change, that life is something to be grasped rather than something that happens, and that we have maximum impact when we work together for the common good. This sense of agency plays out at three scales as it affects the future of the individual, their community (local and national), and their planet (TCLT, UK).

Students' agency as political actors was recognised through their participation in demonstrations, debates, and contributions to the Student Council (MST, DK; CF, IT), and their inclusion in 'House Councils' which represented a form of local democracy (EE, DK). It was also evinced through their involvement in democratic budgetary decision-making processes (PBS, PT) and by providing them with opportunities to engage in a simulated republican political system (YR, PT). Moreover, it was recognised through creative expression such as, for example, organising school festivals whereby students were the protagonists who enjoyed total decision-making power over the content of the festival including the budget, logistics, and social media pages (NSQ, IT), and even through performing a show which portrayed the challenges of adolescence based on the stories and perspectives of many teenagers, educators and social workers (PP, IT).

3.1.6 Summary

While the selection of cases was not designed to represent countries more widely, the summary of findings presented here also draws out some points of comparison and contrast across the participating countries where they reveal potential for cross-national learning.

The organisations, educational institutions and projects studied were generally concerned to ensure that young people's voice contributed to decision making and, in many cases, provided publicly available documentation demonstrating how this was implemented in practice. Across the range of measures of youth 'participation', organisations in Portugal and Denmark scored consistently highly, closely followed by Italy. However, specifically on the sub-criterion of youth 'voice', organisations and schools in the UK, which explicitly followed a good practice model of youth voice (e.g. the Lundy model – see Section 2.2), were particularly strong in demonstrating their good practice since they explicitly used the language of youth voice amplification. A number of these organisations and schools were also part of the Lundy Community of Practice, which provided support, resources and peer-to-peer exchange. Such a Community of Practice might be of value in other contexts, even if it was not linked to a single youth participation model. In contrast, we found an unexpectedly weak demonstration of evidence of youth 'voice' among Finnish cases in both organisational and school settings. This may be a paradoxical reflection of the deep embedding of youth participation in the Finnish context. As noted above (see footnote 4), in Finland, all schools and municipalities are required to have a school or youth council (or equivalent). It may be that this creates a relatively high threshold for appearing as good practice whilst the routinisation of these structures may mean their achievements are not flagged in school and organisation promotional materials. Similarly, the relative paucity of reference to activities or achievements of school committees and regional councils among Italian cases studied may be explained by a routinisation of the expression of youth voice via these bodies. This is reflected upon in greater length in Section 4.

In relation to schools, we found evidence that broader programmes implemented by local or national authorities or third sector organisations across a number of schools played a positive role in stimulating innovation in youth participation in the education sector. Examples of such programmes were found in our sample primarily in Italy and Portugal, but also in Denmark, and consistently delivered good practice in youth participation. Potentially, this is a model that could be adopted in other national settings although, the small sample selection for this study means that such projects may already be in place but were simply not selected.

In relation to the criterion of recognition (acknowledgement, respect and reward) of young people's participation, we found that declaratory (policy statements) and practical (showcasing what young people have done) recognition are more common than financial remuneration. This raises the question of whether claims to value young people's expertise in relation to their own lives is treated equally with those adult experts who routinely make decisions about/for them. However, the constraints on schools and community organisations are self-evident and we did find, nonetheless, some good practice in relation to rewarding young people's participation where possible through a range of skills and development opportunities as well as, in rarer cases, paid positions. There was also a strong

commitment, across all countries, to recognising the agency of young people as political actors and promoting young people as role models for participation rather than seeing them solely as objects of political education for future citizenship. This was notably stronger among community organisations than schools in all countries.

3.2 Assessing Intersectional Inclusion in Participation and Deliberation Practices

In order to assess how selected community organisations and schools considered intersectional inclusion in their practices, it was imperative to, firstly, understand if intersectionality was recognised and, if so, how. Secondly, it was necessary to consider how intersectional inclusion was reflected in organisations' and schools' recruitment practices, the accessibility of their spaces of participation and/or deliberation, and young people's sense of 'belonging' in such spaces. Particular attention was paid to how marginalised and excluded young people were approached and included.

3.2.1 Awareness and Recognition of Intersectionality

The selected community organisations and, to some extent, schools, demonstrated **awareness** and recognition of **intersectionality** and the heterogeneity of 'youth' (see Figures 1 and 2, criterion 4.1). Within many **community organisations**, this awareness was demonstrated *implicitly* through their aims, structures and strategies which implicitly recognise the heterogeneity of young people, including their perspectives and needs (RC, UK; BY, UK; YM, PT; DFUU, DK). For example, reaching out to young people from minority ethnic backgrounds who live in under-resourced neighbourhoods is indicative of such recognition (DGIC, DK). It could also be evident through an organisation's videos, website, and the diversity of its team members and volunteers (PP, UK).

Although intersectionality is not always explicitly mentioned, there is overwhelming evidence that supports a community organisation's awareness of the heterogeneity of youth. This is evinced in two local authorities in the UK (WVC, UK; WC, UK). The former actively reaches out to various marginalised young people where its *Children and Young People's Participation and Co-Production Strategy* states that:

Services should proactively target those facing the greatest barriers to getting involved. For example, younger children, children and young people from minority ethnic backgrounds, those living in disadvantaged neighbourhoods, children missing school, young people in the youth justice system, refugees, traveller children, and disabled children with special needs.

Despite not explicitly referring to or using the term intersectionality, it is palpably present. The latter (WC, UK) actively recognises the heterogeneity of youth, without labelling it as intersectional as such, in its initiatives that target diverse groups of young people ranging from children in care, young people with Special Educational Needs and Disabilities (SEND), young LGBT+ people, to young people from different minority ethnic backgrounds, including asylum seekers, refugees, and young people from Eastern Europe, Africa, Asia and the Middle East. To reiterate, despite intersectionality, as a term, not being explicitly used, it is present.

Some **community organisations** explicitly recognised the heterogeneity of youth by directly referring to intersectionality as a key term. For example, YFNW (UK)'s *Democracy Resource Pack* contains a youth-friendly section entitled *Intersectionality* that explains the origins of the term in black feminism, how it recognises overlapping forms of oppression, and references the centrality of power to intersectionality:

Intersectionality acknowledges a person's range of social identities (e.g. gender, race, sexuality, etc.) as a whole, rather than considering them as separate pieces [...] Intersectionality identifies advantages and disadvantages that are felt by people due to a combination of factors as a whole, rather than considering them as separate pieces (YFNW, UK).

This recognition can also be explicitly stated in community organisations' strategy documents such as in *Strategy 2024-2027* (BN, UK) which outlines the organisation's cross-cutting focus on children and young people from minority ethnic backgrounds:

[o]ur services must be inclusive, accessible, targeted where necessary, and delivered by people who understand the needs of children and young people from all backgrounds and communities, including those who are Black, Minoritised Ethnic, LGBT+ and/or disabled (BN, UK).

Another notable example is a manifesto (CM, PT) that states it 'respects all people, all gender identities and all sexual orientations, respecting and celebrating all cultures, social, economic origins and ethnicities'.

Awareness was also expressed through artistic and creative methods. For example, the 'Multiple Voices' project (YB, DK) published a collection of novels that focused on young people's experiences of marginalisation (due to being a refugee, suffering from a chronic disease, or dropping out of education). These books gave young people a voice to express their experiences of marginalisation as well as a medium to build awareness of the uniqueness of such experiences. Music, film, and photography were utilised to empower vulnerable and marginalised young people by encouraging them to use artistic forms to express the multiplicity of their voices, experiences, and perspectives (TT, DK), in addition to a radio station (RS, IT) that scheduled programmes covering issues ranging from gender stereotypes, violence against young women and gender dysphoria, to diversity and inclusion within Italian cinema.

A number of **community organisations** demonstrated **awareness** through their focus on specific social categories of exclusion. These revolved around gender, sexuality, race/ethnicity, and language. In terms of gender, focus groups and workshops helped facilitate reflections on gender inequalities, gender stereotypes, and gender as a social construct (SYC, FI; X-C, IT; IPGI, IT; PA, PT; YPP, PT). For LGBTQI+, IPGI (IT) published a series of recommendations on the rights of young LGBTQI+ people such as ensuring equal rights between the children of same-sex couples and of heterosexual couples, protecting unaccompanied young migrants who have been persecuted or whose rights have been restricted due to their sexuality, and adopting adequate means to counter hate speech, especially of a

homophobic nature. One community organisation (IOP, IT) focused on the intersections of race and gender, and specifically the experiences and challenges facing young migrant women in attaining education and employment as evinced in this participant's reflections:

Regarding my own journey as a migrant and a woman, I can say that it is difficult. For example, when I have meetings [...] with engineers and managers, when I enter the room, they think I am the secretary. So, I introduce myself by saying 'I am the Head Assessor', usually I am the youngest and always the only woman. This country is not prepared for the fact that a woman can reach managerial roles: women always stop at a certain point, they never get higher than that. So, it is difficult. As a young person, as a woman, as a migrant, it is complicated but not impossible. It can be done, you just have to be determined [...] (IOP, IT).

In terms of recognising race/ethnicity, the 'School of Politics' (YPP, PT) was developed in response to claims made by a young person about migrants 'stealing jobs' from Portuguese natives. The *Democracy Education Guide* (CM, FI) was developed to engage young people (aged 15-29) who had recently moved to Finland, in order to help them better understand the Finnish political system and their rights and responsibilities as well as develop language skills that would empower them to participate in politics.

Finally, and connected to the previous example, awareness of the heterogeneity of youth was demonstrated through organisations paying attention to the power of language and its impact on young people from marginalised backgrounds, including young LGBTQI+ people (IPGI, IT). This is highlighted in a project evaluation report (PA, PT) which calls for translating training resources into local languages (other than English), so as to ensure that trainers have access to resources in their own language which would enable them to better understand and adapt activities in ways that avoid ethnocentrism. The report additionally considers gendered language and the importance of avoiding communicating gender in a binary way which does not consider it to exist on a continuum. For example, using the terms 'ideal man' or 'ideal woman' could be considered an offensive and outdated notion.

Overall, the selected **schools** did not perform as strongly in terms of **awareness** when compared to the community organisations (see Figure 2, above). Nonetheless, some selected schools demonstrated **awareness implicitly** through their policy and strategy documents and websites which emphasised the diversity and promotion of equality regardless of disability, race/ethnicity, gender, sexuality, and health (including mental health) (NC, UK; H&RS, DK; PP, IT; LA, IT). Moreover, others were more explicit. For example, one UK educational trust's *Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Policy* states that:

Understanding and tackling the different barriers which could lead to unequal outcomes for those people who have protected characteristics within the school, while celebrating and valuing the achievements and strengths of all members of the school community, is the key to our approach. Those people with protected characteristics are defined as those who may be susceptible to discrimination because of their age, sex, race, disability, religion or belief, sexual orientation, gender confirmation, pregnancy or maternity, less able or socio-economic background (TCLT, UK).

It continues by stating its objective to be to:

Celebrate diversity and promote (where appropriate) the positive contribution of different ethnic minority groups to the curriculum area, as well as profiling the positive contributions made to society by other minority groups [...] Pastoral staff to take account of all abilities, gender, religious and racial differences, sexual orientation and the experience and needs of particular groups such as Gypsy Roma and Traveller, refugee and asylum seeker pupils (TCLT, UK).

Another UK school's Equality, Diversity and Inclusion objectives include:

To introduce groups/structures across the academy so that stakeholders with different characteristics are represented and have a voice (e.g. LGBTQ groups/student diversity council). To promote a diverse set of viewpoints so that students can hear from, read about and experience the thoughts and views from a varied set of thinkers [...] Prepare students for life in a diverse society by encouraging respect for linguistic, cultural and religious diversity that exists in local communities and the wider world (CABV, UK).

An interesting example was reported in Portugal (SV@DGE, PT) whereby **awareness** was demonstrated through student proposals presented to the Directorate General of Education (DGE) which reflected students' concerns regarding issues of inclusion within their schools. In their meetings with the DGE, when asked about their priorities if they were to become the Minister of Education, some students responded by saying they 'would facilitate accessibility for students with reduced mobility, and create better conditions for everyone by adapting programs to promote uniformity of opportunities'. Others suggested enhancing the support provided to migrant students in order to help them integrate into school life, amongst other proposals calling for stronger inclusivity.

It is evident from the examples presented above that intersectionality and the heterogeneity of youth is recognised by many selected community organisations, but not necessarily schools. This awareness was demonstrated in explicit and implicit ways which suggests the need to widen approaches to how intersectionality is demonstrated, communicated, and embedded within participatory and deliberative practices. Crucially, it is imperative to also assess how this **awareness** is translated into recruitment practices, accessibility of participation spaces, and young people's sense of 'belonging'. In other words, inclusion.

3.2.2 Inclusion and Recruitment

How young people, especially those who are marginalised and excluded, are recruited to the selected community organisations and schools represents a key 'inclusion' criteria. Not only is it important to understand the adopted **recruitment** methods (e.g. self-selection, open invitation, random sampling), but whether efforts are also being made to reach out to marginalised youth or those who would not put themselves forward to participate in such activities. In terms of recruitment methods, open invitation and, as a result, self-selection, were found to be the most popular within the selected **community organisations** (YB, DK; WDD, DK; RAP, DK; PP, UK; WVC, UK; SN, IT; IOP, IT; RS, IT; ABC, IT; TM,

PT; UBN, PT; YPP, PT; PA, PT; CM, PT; YM, PT; KYC, FI). One community organisation invited over 90,000 young people in Copenhagen in an attempt to make it representative:

In the Summer of 2021, all young people in the city received an invitation via e-Boks [Denmark's provider of secure platforms and digital post boxes]. 804 of the city's young people wanted to actively participate in this democratic experiment – before, during and after the 2021 municipal elections. That's an impressive number in itself! (WDD, DK).

The 26 representative young people were then selected by stratified random sampling to take part in the citizens' assembly, which was based on the parameters of gender, age, education, and origin.

Despite being open invitation, a number of community organisations implemented specific criteria that were based on age (IPGI, IT; YM, PT; KYC, FI; SYC, FI; TYCI, FI; YCV, FI; YCP, FI; HYI, FI; SC, UK), being enrolled in schools or universities (TM, PT; VYP, PT), belonging to a certain locality (VYP, PT; YM, PT; SYC, FI; TYCI, FI; YCV, FI; YCP, FI; HYI, FI; SC, UK), and being involved in participatory initiatives at local or national level (IPGI, IT). An interesting example was found in Italy (ID, IT) where personal invitations were sent by the mayor to all young people aged between 12 and 24 living in the area to promote participation opportunities. Some selected community organisations utilised their websites and social media to advertise and recruit young people (YB, DK; DFUU, DK; AOYH, DK; AF, UK; PP, UK; WVC, UK; WC, UK; SN, IT), whilst others actively recruited through existing networks of partners and/or third parties (e.g. other community organisations, local authorities, schools, parents or young people who have previously engaged with their services) (AOYH, DK; UD, DK; AF, UK; PP, UK; WVC, UK; SN, IT; X-C, IT).

The majority of the selected community organisations made efforts to reach out to marginalised youth. These included community organisations that targeted marginalised young people in general (BY, UK; PP, UK; RAP, DK; WC, UK; LCC, UK), young people living in marginalised and vulnerable neighbourhoods (DGIC, DK; TT, DK), disabled young people and those with special educational needs (AOYH, DK; WVC, UK; SC, UK), young people leaving care (SC, UK), young people with migrant and/or refugee backgrounds (DFUU, DK; WC, UK; X-C, IT), and young working-class people or young people from lower socio-economic backgrounds (RC, UK). One local authority's *Participation Toolkit* succinctly summarises the need to engage with young people who might otherwise be marginalised:

There is a danger that only the most motivated groups, powerful people, strongest opinions or loudest voices are heard or considered. Decision makers should involve everyone with an interest, especially those individuals and community including children and young people and, especially those at risk of marginalisation whose voices are more seldom included. Without a full range of perspectives, decisions may be unfairly balanced in favour of certain groups – or may unwittingly create barriers for others (SC, UK).

Nonetheless, given the nature and limitations of this report's analysis, it was unclear how some community organisations did engage with these groups in practice.

For the selected **schools**, open invitation (self-selection) also represented the most widely used recruitment method (PBS, PT; SV@DGE, PT; SWV, PT; SS, FI; RSKC, FI). Some schools were found

to automatically include all students via School/Class Assemblies (YR, PT; SA, PT) or particular projects (PS, FI; LS, FI) thus raising questions about whether students are able to opt out (i.e. take part voluntarily). There was a lack of evidence in regard to selected schools reaching out to marginalised youth or to those would not put themselves forward. The exception was H&RS (DK) which specifically targeted 'late bloomers' (i.e. mature students), young people from lower socio-economic backgrounds, and those with learning disabilities.

Interestingly, a number of schools were found to have an established process for selecting student representatives. For example, representatives of each class could be voted for directly by the students (SWV, PT; YR, PT; SA, PT). Students could put themselves forward for leadership positions via a written application or a video application process. This would be followed by a democratic election campaign during which candidates canvassed the student body to vote for them (CABV, UK). Similarly, students can be elected to become House Officials and members of the Pupil Senior Leadership Team (BBMS, UK), or become members of the Student Council by submitting letters of intent followed by interviews and selection by the School's Senior Leadership Team (AA, UK).

3.2.3 Accessibility

The ability to ensure equality of opportunity and the **accessibility** of participation spaces for those with additional needs (including using accessible language) represents a second key 'inclusion' criterion that was assessed. Equality of opportunity was explicitly outlined in the policy and strategy documents, websites and videos of a number of **community organisations** (DGI, DK; AOYH, DK; DFUU, DK; TT, DK; AID, DK; YFNW, UK; BN, UK; PP, UK; WVC, UK; SC, UK; LCC, UK; SYC, FI). In some cases, equality of opportunity was implied within the documents rather than explicitly stated (WDD, DK; DUC, DK; WC, UK; UBN, PT; MP, PT; YPP, PT; VYP, PT). The importance of offering accessible (physical) participation spaces was highlighted by a number of community organisations. For example, the *Participation Toolkit* (SC, UK) calls on local authorities to ensure that 'opportunities to participate are accessible, fair and impartial including accessible venues. This includes time, date, venue, accessible toilets, parking, food and refreshments, digital requirements, equality and diversity and cultural needs recognised and met'. Another local authority's participation strategy (WC, UK) outlined the importance of having spaces that are accessible to young people with additional needs, and to develop age-appropriate and accessible information. Similarly, in the *Training and Strategy* document (LCC, UK), it states that 'Children and young people must have access to safe spaces to meet so they have equal opportunities to formulate and express views'.

One community organisation (TT, DK) made its participation space more accessible by embedding its 'culture labs' in the under-resourced neighbourhoods it served so that young people could access its services without having to travel far. Whilst another (AID, DK) made its spaces accessible by offering participants an array of activities that ranged from film and game nights to organising debates, which it believed to have enabled young people from different backgrounds to take part depending on their interests and needs. Utilising accessible (online) participation spaces were also prioritised:

At [PP, UK] we enjoy telling the story behind our numbers to add depth, balance and insight. Our playful in practice approach means we often leverage memes, short engaging

infographics, and easy-to-read reports co-created with young people to present our findings [...] We strive to utilise the right platforms and communication tools, including youth-proofing our language, as part of our unique approach. By incorporating memes and other creative means of expression, we tap into Gen Z's preferences and communication styles, ensuring that their voices are heard and their ideas are effectively conveyed. This commitment to innovative and inclusive methodologies forms the essence of our 'secret sauce' in connecting with and empowering young people. (PP, UK)

Providing accessible online spaces was also emphasised by (WVC, UK) which offered members of its Youth Council the opportunity to attend meetings either face to face or online (hybrid) 'to allow those who are placed out of the city to participate regardless of how far they may be'. Whilst online consultations were offered by (IPGI, IT) which encouraged more young people to participate given its anonymity.

A large number of selected community organisations emphasised the importance of using plain, clear, direct, and accessible language as a way of enhancing accessibility (DFUU, DK; WDD, DK; AF, UK; YFNW, UK; BN, UK; PP, UK; WVC, UK; LCC, UK; TM, PT; ID, IT), as well as providing language interpretation services (WDD, DK; SYC, FI; TYCI, FI; YCP, FI; HYI, FI). Developing more 'youth proof' documents to ensure accessibility was emphasised in the guidelines for engagement used by a number of organisations:

Language proficiency should not hinder participation in addressing themes. Provide opportunities for everyone to participate regardless of their language skills. Simultaneously, it's important to note that all exercises and themes are suitable for participants at the beginning stages of language learning. Exercises in the guide aim to accommodate simplified language [...] Use plain language and explain the terms you use. Be concrete and illustrate your points with images or activities. Ensure that language and concepts support equality (CM, FI).

Children and young people must be provided with full, accessible, diversity-sensitive and age-appropriate information (YFNW, UK).

Relevant information should be made available to children and young people. It should be at the right time, in the right format, no jargon, culturally appropriate and accessible (WVC, UK).

Equality of opportunity was explicitly referenced in some selected **schools'** policy and strategy documents (H&RS, DK; MST, DK; LA, IT; PBS, PT; YR, PT; TCLT, UK; AA, UK)

We will promote the concept of equality of opportunity throughout the student body through curriculum provision and through the ethos and values demonstrated by the Academy [...] We seek to develop an understanding of, and promotion of, human equality and equal opportunities (CABV, UK).

Only a handful of selected **schools** considered issues surrounding accessible participation spaces. For example, in its *Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion* document, one educational trust states the importance

of 'the school providing an environment in which all pupils have equal access to all facilities and resources [...] steps are taken to ensure that all pupils have access to mainstream curriculum by taking into account the cultural and lifestyle backgrounds of all pupils, their linguistic needs and their learning styles' (TCLT, UK). However, more schools acknowledged the use of plain, clear, direct, and accessible language as a way of enhancing accessibility (H&RS, DK; MST, DK; EE, DK; RSKC, FI), with a few offering language interpretation (H&RS, DK; TCLT, UK).

3.2.4 Belonging

The ability to ensure that young people have a sense of **belonging** in participation spaces comprises another central criterion used to assess inclusion. This sense of belonging is dependent on having spaces that are comfortable, welcoming, and safe for young people. Efforts to ensure belonging were identified in the aims and strategies of a number of **community organisations**, particularly in Denmark (DGIC, DK; AOYH, DK; AID, DK). For example, DFUU (DK) utilises 'Udtaler' (Speakers) as a method to help develop strong communities where young people from refugee backgrounds are able to engage in debates and learn how to influence opinions. Accordingly, and through their engagement, they would feel a sense of belonging to that community and capable of bringing about change. The same organisation additionally organises social camps, workshops, buddy-programmes, food events, sports events and peer-to-peer activities to strengthen young people's participation within their local community.

Community organisations worked towards ensuring a sense of belonging through art and creative expression, with one cooperating with a music festival to offer young people, especially those from minority ethnic backgrounds, an opportunity to feel they belong: 'I have goosebumps, I don't feel alien anymore [...] Music is the medium that really connects us across all our differences' (RAP, DK). Creative expression was also used by another community project to help strengthen the sense of belonging amongst young people from minoritised backgrounds based on the recognition that art and music are mediums through which social relations could be developed and solidarity established (TT, DK). Another example is found in Italy (X-C, IT) where silk-screen printing workshops are utilised to offer young people a way to communicate their experiences by translating them into images.

Many selected community organisations outlined their efforts to ensure participation spaces were comfortable, welcoming and safe for young people (UBN, PT; UYHN, PT; VYP, PT; DFUU, DK; IPGI, IT; CL, IT). For example, the *Empathy Programme* (BY, UK) commits to creating 'shared, non-judgemental spaces for young people to meet and interact' in order to 'build safer, more inclusive communities'. Supporting young people in campaigning for spaces that are comfortable and to which they feel they belong is central to one community organisation's aims as stated in their *Listen Up! Manifesto*'s demand for 'access to spaces that are ours' (RC, UK). Their *Our Space* project is also dedicated to helping 'create inclusive and accessible public spaces for working-class young people', which are characterised by 'access, representation, safety, understanding and respect' (RC, UK). The importance of peer-to-peer support and youth-led workshops was also acknowledged as being helpful in developing safe and comfortable participation spaces for young people (VYP, PT; DUC, DK; DGIC, DK; AID, DK; LQ, IT).

The Lundy Model (see Section 2) has been adopted by several community organisations in the UK as an evidence-based framework for ensuring that all space is inclusive and safe (AF, UK; YFNW, UK; PP, UK; WC, UK). Unsurprisingly, providing safe and inclusive spaces featured prominently in these organisations' strategy documents and policies:

Children, young people, parents and carers are more likely to stay engaged when they feel safe, respected and listened to. Our implementation of the Lundy Model will facilitate this, providing the building blocks to dismantle the systems that leave some voices unheard (AF, UK).

In Finland, *Safer Space Principles* were outlined by two organisations (YCV, FI; CM, FI). The former states that its principles were developed in collaboration with youth councillors and approved by the Youth Council and addresses issues relating to bullying and discrimination, accepting people's differences without prejudice, and establishing common rules on how to involve everyone in discussions and activities (YCV, FI). The latter states that:

Topics related to society and politics often divide opinions. The purpose of safer space principles is to make people think proactively about their responsibility and respectful behaviour. These principles help create an atmosphere where each participant can feel safe and comfortable to contribute as themselves [...] A safer space is achieved when diversity, accessibility, language awareness, different learning styles, and general ethical guidelines are considered (CM, FI).

In terms of **schools**, there was some evidence of acknowledging the importance of having welcoming and safe spaces for students, especially when concerning their learning and schooling experiences:

We value diversity and believe that equality in [TCLT, UK] should permeate all aspects of school life and is the responsibility of every member of the school and wider community. Every member of the school community should feel safe, secure, valued and of equal worth.

Efforts to ensure a sense of belonging were identified in the policy and strategy documents as well as website of some schools (FBHS, DK; H&RS, DK; MST, DK; EE, DK). This was particularly evident in one school's Equality, Diversity and Inclusivity objectives, which state that it aims 'to create and embed a diverse curriculum that is inclusive for all and widens our students' understanding of the world', and 'to introduce groups/structures across the academy so that stakeholders with different characteristics are represented and have a voice (e.g., LGBTQ groups/student diversity council)' (CABV, UK). Another school (BBMS, UK) utilised the 'House System'⁸ as a way of developing students' sense of belonging alongside having well-being and anti-bullying ambassadors who play an integral role in ensuring that other students feel safe, supported, and respected.

⁸ This system allocates each student to one of several 'houses' for the duration of their time at school. Houses compete against each other in various academic and extracurricular activities, developing a sense of belonging and solidarity amongst students.

Some selected schools have found the adoption of small group dynamics to be helpful in providing comfortable spaces for students, especially those who struggle to voice their opinions in large groups (YR, PT) and, similarly to community organisations, others have found art and creative expression (RSKC, FI), peer-to-peer support, and student-led initiatives (SA, PT) to be effective. For example, FHS (DK) boasts a strong student assembly – comprised of all students – which has a strong say in the running of the school, including the curriculum. It is deemed to be a ‘student-led’ school where students have the freedom to decorate their classrooms, discuss rules, draft class charters on anti-bullying and addressing discrimination against gender, race, and sexual orientation. This contributes to enhancing students’ sense of belonging and ownership of their school.

3.2.5 Summary

The heterogeneity of youth is recognised by many selected community organisations. There was evident awareness that structural disadvantage is intersectional and efforts were made to reach out to marginalised youth and to ensure equality of opportunity, for example, through accessibility of participation spaces for those with additional needs (including using accessible language) and making spaces safe and comfortable for all. While no evaluation of organisations and schools is undertaken in this study, there are a number of comparisons and contrasts between organisations and schools and between different national contexts that it might be illustrative to note.

Community organisations in Denmark demonstrated most awareness and recognition of intersectionality (even if not always explicitly). Indeed, there was a wider tendency for this awareness to be demonstrated implicitly only. This suggests the need to widen approaches to how intersectionality is demonstrated, communicated, and embedded within participatory and deliberative practices. Schools generally demonstrated less awareness of intersectionality than community organisations although Portugal was an exception to this rule and performed most positively on this criterion among selected schools.

Community organisations were generally stronger in terms of reaching out and recruiting marginalised and excluded young people than schools. However, it remains difficult for organisations and schools to avoid ‘self-selection’ bias when opening participation to all and the desk-based nature of this study makes it challenging to assess how successful organisations and schools were in engaging with more marginalised groups of young people in practice. Significant attention to providing safe and inclusive spaces for youth participation was found in documentation across our cases in all country contexts. UK and Finnish organisations and schools might be highlighted for their attention to creating safe spaces while on the criterion of creating a sense of ‘belonging’, community organisations in Portugal and schools in Denmark are notable for their good practice.

3.3 Understanding the Strengths and Limitations of Challenging Systemic Exclusion through Youth Participation and Deliberation

The cases selected for this study all reflect good practice in encouraging and amplifying youth voice that goes on across community organisations, local authorities, youth-focused charities and umbrella

organisations as well as in schools. All of this is to be applauded not least in times of financial austerity when youth provision and services are so often the first to be seen as dispensable. One of the aims of this study, however, was to ask challenging questions about how far systemic exclusion of young people, especially exclusion rooted in intersectional structural disadvantage, can be addressed through youth participation and deliberation. In this final section, therefore, we consider evidence as to how organisations and schools ensure that their practices lead to young people's voices being heard and having an influence. We then reflect on whether there is unfulfilled potential for the critical dimensions of deliberative practice and intersectional thinking to empower a more sustained challenge to young people's exclusion and the constraints faced by organisations and schools in breaking down those barriers.

3.3.1 Being heard and having an impact

It is essential that young people are not only allowed a voice but that their voice is heard. While it is axiomatic that the organisations and schools selected for our study were committed to putting in place processes for enabling youth voice and participation, it does not necessarily follow that all have robust systems for monitoring whether or not that voice has an impact. In analysing the materials we gathered from the cases, we sought to gather evidence of the influence of youth participation using two measures: i) evidence of a system for monitoring and documenting the impact of young people's participation; and ii) concrete evidence of the outcome of youth voice, for example, through illustrations of what had changed as a result of young people's participation.

The commitment and process underpinning good practice in ensuring participation is impactful was summed up in one UK Local Authority's Participation Strategy by stating: 'We use the term participation not simply to mean "taking part" or "being present" but as having some influence over decisions and action' (SC, UK). A key element of its model for ensuring young people know what the extent, and limits, of their engagement has been, is feedback:

We will tell you how your involvement has been used and the outcomes. You will be able to see the difference that your involvement has made. This will include follow up emails, you said we did information, reports and documents (SC, UK).

Among selected **organisations**, those bodies supporting youth voice in feeding directly into regional authority structures were often most open in documenting both what they had achieved and how they monitored this, to ensure 'that children, young people and families can check whether their voice is being acted upon or not' (WVC, UK). In some cases, this included making public the minutes of meetings reviewing the working of the body and proposals adopted (ABC, IT; ID, IT; YZ, IT). UK local authorities delivering youth participation were particularly strong in setting out clearly in their participation approaches, the mechanisms in place to ensure that young people's views are taken seriously and acted upon and thus have influence. Such mechanisms included actioning recommendations from formal participation groups and explaining if changes could not be made; ensuring that plans about young people are shaped by what they say; inviting young people to evaluate services they receive and feedback their opinions; and providing feedback about decisions made including annual 'You Said, We Did' documents (LCC, UK; WC, UK).

These local authorities were among a number of UK organisations that had adopted or adapted the Lundy model of children's and young people's participation, one key dimension of which is 'Influence'. The importance of this model is also evident among community and charity organisations. For example, one organisation, working with young people on mental health issues, states in its participation strategy that: 'We hear and act on their [children, young people and families] voices at every stage of our work, and their perspectives influence the decisions we make' (AF, UK). The organisation has a number of Champions' panels and 'huddles' as well as Ambassadors' groups and a Participation Steering Group that work at project and organisation level to ensure a constant process of monitoring how young people's voice is being heard, by whom and with what impact. Another organisation working with disadvantaged children and young people has a dedicated 'Voice and Influence' team as well as documents evincing examples of young people's deliberation in key decisions of the organisation from corporate strategy to recruitment (BN, UK). A third organisation which is responsible for delivering a regional authority's Children and Young People's Voice and Participation programme, sets out clear guidelines for monitoring outcome including that monitoring should be done together with young people (YFNW, UK). These and other organisations selected for study provide details of numerous examples of how young people's voice was heard and led to changes in fields of health and mental health, transport, urban regeneration, poverty, discrimination and anti-racism, delays in the criminal justice system, school attendance and domestic conflict (MP, PT; YFNW, UK; PA, PT; X-C, IT; SC, UK).

Of course, this does not mean that more routinised modes of deliberation and participation, for example, those embedded in student councils, hearings and panels do not have an important impact on the young people who engage with them. This is particular especially within the Danish and Finnish contexts included in this study whereby participatory processes may already be embedded in classic deliberative approaches to participation, as opposed to empowerment-based ones, which develops a strong sense among young people that they are being listened to and included in decisions that are important to them. Arguably, this reflects a wider shift in young people's political participation (at least in some parts of Europe) from a predominantly ideological to more strategic engagement (Lieberkind, 2021: 78). Lieberkind's analysis of International Civic and Citizenship Education Study (ICCS) data⁹, for example, shows that Danish students score highest on measures of both the extent to which they deliberate political and social issues with parents and friends, and the extent to which they think their classroom environment is open to and stimulates debate (ibid.: 83). They also score highest on civic knowledge, which is a crucial element of internal efficacy. It is important, therefore, to recognise that empowering students, in terms of facilitating their competence to know about, have an interest in and deliberate on decisions and the decision-making system, may result in their support for, not desire to challenge or transform, the formalised and conventional system (ibid.: 89-90).

A number of community organisations indicated that they had been subject to external evaluation of their impact (UBN, PT; YPP, PT; DFUU, DK; DGIC, DK; AID, DK). In one case, the evidence of impact was substantial including videos, input of young people to local councils and national political fora,

⁹ This is a comparative, quantitative study of Grade 8 students' knowledge, attitudes to society, and the ways in which they are prepared to undertake their roles as citizens in a democracy. The data cited here comes from the 2016 survey in involving 84,000 students in 24 countries.

including televised political debates (AID, DK). Others relied on feedback from participants to monitor impact (UYHN, PT; YM, PT). The latter might indicate a blurred line between where participation is successful in as much as participants felt that they are being heard and where participation has had a demonstrable impact on policy or practice. The importance of not equating these two is perhaps indicated in one case, where feedback gathered during monitoring noted: 'We feel like we are being heard. Now, we also want to see change' (VYP, PT). Two Danish organisations which had strong evaluation policies indicate that being heard and having an impact are two different measures. In the first case, the outcomes include concrete examples of where the young people with refugee background had been given the opportunity to express their experiences and political views, but examples of where their voice had led to actual changes is sparse (DFUU, DK). In the second case, the evaluation report evinces a range of outcomes for young people (in terms of making relationships and developing personal skills), but does not indicate any political influence outcomes (DGIC, DK). As noted above, it is important not to assume that young people's voices being heard would necessarily result in change, even radical change, but rather their voices might confirm satisfaction with the status quo. What is essential is to be clear about what the objectives of participatory programmes are in terms of voice and impact and that evaluation captures both whether this is achieved and whether the objective is appropriately ambitious.

In those countries where there was a strong monitoring of impact, we found substantial evidence of what had changed as a result of participation. The exception is Finland, where generally low evidence of monitoring of influence was accompanied by strong demonstration of outcomes especially among local authority fora (e.g. KYC, FI; SYC, FI; TYC, FI; YCV, FI; YP, FI) and other community organisations (GG, FI; LP, FI). It is possible that in these cases, alongside others providing concrete evidence of the impact of young people's voice (PP, UK; YPP, PT; AOYH, DK), that monitoring is simply not always available publicly. This is certainly the case with regard to the Danish territory of youth self-governance (UD, DK), where the territory itself is living proof of the influence young people have. Similarly, it may not be the case that those organisations scoring lowly on 'Outcome' are failing to ensure that their youth voice processes have an impact, but simply that their documentation does not provide concrete examples or case studies provided of such influence (e.g. BY, UK; DD, PT; IOP, IT). The project could also be too early in its implementation to demonstrate any impact (CM, PT). These examples raise, once again, the issue of whether in countries where classic youth deliberative and decision-making forums are already deeply embedded in society, outcomes are thus not articulated in documentation as impacts and achievements per se, but rather their mundaneness speaks to the long-term impact they make.

Among **schools**, it is perhaps not surprising that those cases which appear to have the greatest influence are those which are part of the wider authority-led projects selected for study in Portugal and Italy. For example, the Participatory Budget project in Portugal undertakes an annual official audit of a sample of schools, with the aim of evaluating the impact of the measure and producing recommendations for its improvement. Outcomes are showcased in a series of videos demonstrating how students' participation made concrete changes including, *inter alia*, the installation of a visual signal of the start of classes to improve the lives of deaf students (PBS, PT). In Italy, the programme run by

Save the Children to promote active citizenship in classrooms also had thorough monitoring and evaluation processes in place with tools for assessment made available and concrete examples of outcomes of projects published by participating schools (CF, IT).

However, individual schools also monitor student voice through peer and teacher monitoring and disseminate its outcome, for example, through the school newspaper (SA, PT) or Instagram profile (FBHS, DK). In one UK school, the Senior School Leadership Team updates the Student Council noticeboard with 'You said, we did!' messages and year group representatives feedback to year groups assembly and the Student Council places information on social media and also provides feedback to the Board of Governors at the end of the year (BBMS, UK). Concrete projects realised as a result of student voice decisions are also detailed (SWV, PT; TCLT, UK; AS, FI) including outcomes beyond the school, as in the case of an advocacy project run by one of the Finnish schools, which led to the reversal of a decision by the municipality to start charging for school trips (RSKC, FI).

Practical and visual documentation of impact were evident in a number of cases including a public festival showcasing the ideas of the young people (NSQ, IT) and videos illustrating examples of where young people's voices have been listened to, such as by getting access to student cards, mobilising a demonstration etc. (MST, DK). Informal, celebratory events are also used as an opportunity to remember the work done and evaluate activities (SS, FI).

3.3.2 Critique: challenging structural inequality

As noted in Section 3.1.4 and Section 3.2, when assessing both deliberative practices and attention to intersectionality, we included a sub-criterion of 'critique'. In analysing deliberative activities, this criterion was designed to understand whether deliberation went beyond seeking consensus and aimed to expose structural power relations with the objective of empowering young people to challenge inequalities stemming from them. In relation to 'intersectionality', we sought to assess the extent to which the selected community organisations and schools recognise the critical nature of intersectionality, as in its ability to expose the multiple, interwoven power structures as a transformative process. In both cases, the aim was to establish the extent to which the limits of deliberation without structural change are recognised. This analysis revealed that, in general, where deliberative practices were found, they were often not accompanied by this critical dimension and in terms of intersectionality, both community organisations and schools were generally more likely to show awareness of the heterogeneity of 'youth' and the intersectional nature of exclusion than embrace its critical capacity to expose interwoven power structures.

A small number of **organisations** studied did recognise the capacity and intention of the deliberative fora and activities in which they engaged to allow the opening up discussion of systemic or structural inequalities and how they might be addressed. The Danish organisation described above as including two deliberative (formal youth councils and youth communities), for example, had an 'empowerment' Freirean-inspired approach at the heart of which critiques power and aims to challenge structural power that confines minorities to so called 'ghetto areas' (AID, DK). One of the UK based organisations also makes explicit reference to the importance of empowering young people and that campaigns challenge

existing power structures (RC, UK). For example, the website describes its campaign activity as designed to:

give working-class young people the opportunity to harness their skills, learn about the power of campaigning and challenge institutions, systems and structures to create a fair and class-inclusive world.

One particular campaign, entitled *Listen Up!*, includes a demand for the delivery (and equal entitlement to) 'critical thinking and citizenship learning' in new educational programmes being proposed locally (RC, UK). This focus on critique is evident also in one of the Portuguese projects studied, which asks participants to consider underlying factors that hinder political participation (UYHN, PT). There is also evidence of conceptual reflection regarding the tendency of institutions to reject 'dissonant, non-conforming voices' in a community-led health initiative in Italy (CL, IT).

However, this formulation of deliberative practice falls well short of recognising the 'structural limits of deliberation' (Drake, 2023: 96). Indeed, quite notably, some of the more radical self-government projects (such as the UD, DK) do not have critical deliberative practices built into their activities. Others, engage with issues and experts that are very critical of established conditions and politics but do not go beyond consensus seeking in their dialogic approach (e.g. WDD, DK). Perhaps most surprisingly, some projects that are strongly focused on promoting political engagement, do not include a critique of structural power relations (e.g. MP, PT) or start from the position of understanding contemporary democracy as being based on structural inequality rather than equality (Banerjee, 2021). Others have an apparently critical agenda (e.g. challenging racism, discrimination, intolerance) but their activities do not consciously contribute to critique or critical deliberation (e.g. PA, PT; X-C, IT).

A number of community organisations explicitly recognised the critical nature of intersectionality in as much as it allows the exposing of multiple, interwoven power structures and that this intersection is not just aggregative but may result in distinct types of oppression. This was evident, for example, in 'resource packs' published by one organisation on topics such as anti-racism and feminism, which address the different forms of inequality and oppression through the discussion of systemic racism and intersectionality: 'Types of prejudice such as sexism or racism do not always exist in isolation, but often combine to form a new type of oppression' (YFNW, UK). Similarly, another community organisation states in one of its strategy documents that:

Some children, families and communities face more challenges on top of this because of structural inequalities and discrimination in society. This can mean they're more likely to have poor health and fewer chances in life (BN, UK).

Where the critical nature of intersectionality was not directly labelled as such, there might be reference to the power structures that underpin the exclusion of young people, particularly working-class young people (RC, UK). However, not even in these cases was the transformative potential of an intersectional lens considered directly.

The critical nature of intersectionality was more likely to be recognised *implicitly* through an organisation's aims. In the case of one project that aimed to give voice and strengthen the democratic

self-efficacy of youth groups, the project demonstrates an explicit intersectional focus on youth and their marginalisation (YB, DK). In another organisation, the recognition is implied through its focus on the structural inequalities facing young people from minority ethnic backgrounds living in deprived neighbourhoods (AID, DK). In both cases, it can be argued, critique is immanent. Recognition can also be implied through an organisation's/project's activities, where young people's participation could encourage them to engage in critical reflection about intersectional exclusion. In one organisation, artistic production allowed participants to visualise the lives of young people from ethnic minority backgrounds in order to illustrate and critique their difficult living conditions (TT, DK). One organisation recognised that an intersectional approach was crucial to the training process, allowing young people, through participation, to become able to identify cases of intersectional discrimination:

Most of them expressed that discrimination based on religion, sexual orientation, gender expression, class, etc. has a negative impact on their own communities [...] A majority of them highlighted that homophobia, LGBTQI-phobia, and anti-Roma sentiments were the most pressing issues in their communities of origin (PA, PT).

The critical nature of intersectionality was also evident in policy-oriented activities such as the drawing up of the General Covenant of Collaboration for the Promotion and Protection of the Rights of LGBTQIA+ people (LQ, IT). This called for stronger intergenerational and intersectional collaborations to support non-binary people, particularly those affected by social loneliness and lack of family support networks. The proposed changes also advocated for utilising data more effectively to promote more inclusive policies and services capable of identifying and addressing 'multiple discrimination' facing LGBTQIA+ people (LQ, IT).

There is also some evidence of organisations recognising the limits of deliberation without structural change especially in relation to the discussion of issues relating to young people with disabilities and young people with refugee backgrounds (AOYH, DK; DFUU, DK). The diversity of issues of concern to young people, and their lived experience that made those issues prominent for them, is recognised also by organisations developing manifestos for change. For example, one such project in Portugal notes that: 'The diversity of contexts and themes selected by the young participants [...] reveals sensitivity, critical spirit and capacity for intervention' (DD, PT). However, significantly, the statement goes on to illustrate the project's critical reflection on the limits of deliberation without structural change:

The project aims to promote active citizenship and leadership among young people, creating opportunities for reflection on their participation in society, identifying existing obstacles, recommending solutions and promoting dialogue between young people and political decision-makers (DD, PT).

Other organisations also recognised the need to widen the scope for participation and overcome structural obstacles to young people's political participation in order to address the challenges imposed by structural power relations and help young people influence political decision making (CM, PT; VYP, PT):

We demand this investment for those who live trapped by the lack of horizons and those who cannot escape poverty. For those who cannot leave their parents' homes, for those who are precarious, and for eternal interns. For those who wanted to stay, and for those who were unable to study. For those who want to do more and better [...] Many of us were the first in our family to finish school, many of us are the result of a collective effort, the pride of the town and city. But we need more. More space, more desire, more attention, more opportunities. More seats at the table (there are plenty of us for dinner!) (CM, PT).

School settings themselves have inherent constraints in challenging structural power relations, not least between adults and young children. This was evident in the documentation reviewed across all countries which revealed little evidence that deliberation goes beyond consensus-seeking or makes visible or challenges structural power relations. Exceptions include one Danish school, which described having different deliberative fora, which allow the power structures between students and teachers, and thereby also between generations to be challenged (FHS, DK). In addition to one Portuguese school where a number of fora were said, *inter alia*, to help students to balance structural power relations in school (YT, PT).

Selected **schools** were not strong in recognising the critical nature of intersectionality. No relevant examples were identified in either UK or Finnish schools selected and in other cases, the reference was brief and superficial (YR, PT; SA, PT; H&RS, DK). Two notable examples were identified. The first recognised the limits of deliberation without structural change implicitly whereby the establishment of the programme itself was in response to ensuring young people had more democratic influence and their voices heard against the backdrop of greater structural barriers and lack of political education opportunities (MST, DK). The second, a theatre and active citizenship project targeting secondary schools provided a powerful indictment of intersectional exclusion in the following declaration:

Dear city, listen to me, you are beautiful but not perfect. Dear city, I am writing to inform you that as many as 126 out of 400 projects deal with inequalities. This means that a great many boys and girls who live there suffer from some form of discrimination, exclusion, violence, people who have some form of disability and still come up against architectural barriers that limit their accessibility. Architectural barriers that limit their mobility and autonomy, and cultural barriers, which stunt their growth and freedom and lead them to exclusion from places, activities and projects, at school and outside. LGBTQI+ people suffer, on whom an ancient hatred is poured, a deep violence, evident in bullying and aggression by those from outside who attack them, and constitutes an even deeper wound when it comes from the family. People who come from other origins or cultures suffer, and so do those born here in your lands, but who have something in their appearance that identifies as foreigners. They too end up fighting a daily battle against what others see in them, and there is no word, no action, not even a passport that saves them from the indelible border. They end up having no land anywhere. To feel at home nowhere. But we know, dear city, that there is home here for everyone, don't we? More or less (PP, IT).

3.3.3 Summary

The evidence gathered from our cases of good practice suggest that organisations, and schools, to a lesser extent, are aware of the importance of monitoring and feeding back to young people the impact of their participation. It seems that adopting formal models (such as the Lundy model among UK organisations) or being directly plugged into local or national policy making structures is important for ensuring impact is monitored and demonstrated. Influence, and the ‘feedback loop’ to young people about the impact of their participation, is seen within the Lundy model as fundamental to the empowerment of young people. This is not restricted to the local authorities and organisations that directly base their approach on the Lundy model as others were also found to place strong emphasis on monitoring and feeding back to young people.

Some of the organisations studied employed external evaluation to assess their impact. While all monitoring and evaluation of influence is beneficial, it is important to take a critical approach to external evaluation rather than assume it acts as a gold standard. Such evaluation could be by process only (i.e. asking whether the programme does what it said it was going to do) rather than subjecting it to substantive, critical assessment of its aims and ambition. External evaluation may also be expensive and driven by ‘value for money’ criteria of funders rather than what participants see as important. Measurement of success, therefore, should also be informed by youth voice. The evidence reviewed raised questions about what exactly is being measured as ‘impact’. Some evaluations focused on the policy or political impact of participation while others emphasised a more subjective sense among young people of having ‘been heard’ but not necessarily as having changed something.

Our findings in relation to whether the critical capacity of both deliberation and intersectionality are recognised and employed by organisations and schools to challenge structural barriers to youth participation, show a weaker picture. Only a small number of organisations studied recognised the capacity and intention of the deliberative fora and activities in which they engaged in to open up discussion of systemic or structural inequalities. There was additionally little evidence in the schools studied that deliberation goes beyond consensus-seeking or makes visible/challenges structural power relations.

Academic research suggests an intersectional approach can reveal how intersections compound young people’s exclusion from our understanding of active ‘citizens’. Nonetheless, it also offers a critical lens that makes visible the interwoven nature of structures of power and opens up new possibilities for participation based on complex emergent social and political identities. While there is evidence that the heterogeneity of ‘youth’ is recognised in the participatory and deliberative practices we studied, the critical nature of intersectionality was generally implicit rather than explicit in the programmes and activities of organisations and almost invisible in the practices within schools.

4 CONCLUSION

The findings of this study for each of its three objectives have been collated in the summary sections above. Here, therefore, we reflect on broader, cross-cutting findings of significance for the next stage

of this work, which is to develop guidelines for the Intersectional Deliberative and Participatory Practices (I-DPP) and Intersectional Participatory Action Research and Deliberation (I-PARD) toolkits, and a framework for the Inclusivity Footprint Calculator. The key challenge of these next steps is how to draw on the wide range of forms of good practice in different settings, whilst seeking to develop a framework and tool that is useful across various national (and local) as well as sectoral (e.g. community, local authority and educational) contexts.

This study demonstrates that the **context** of implementation is crucial to understanding how participation is documented and described. At one level, we might see this as a matter of language and presentation. As noted repeatedly in the discussion of findings, evidence that particular criteria were taken into account may be more or less explicit or implicit. However, to simply recommend that organisations are more explicit in what their objectives and their achievements are in relation, for example, to the recognition of intersectional inclusion or the limits to deliberative practice without structural change, would be to ignore potentially sound reasons for not being explicit. One of these relates to the competing need for accessibility, especially in terms of language. A second concerns the necessarily formal settings – for example, schools – of many youth voice programmes, which constrains the degree to which all power structures are open to challenge.

At a second level, this relates to the **historical and cultural context** of participatory and deliberative youth activities. In contexts where the rights of children and young people to be consulted are already deeply enshrined, the commitment to youth voice may be more subtly embedded in institutional practices and less ‘advertised’ in public documentation. As discussed in Section 3.3, in national contexts where youth voice is already embedded (if not mandatory) in a range of educational, local authority and voluntary sector settings, the practices and outcomes of youth or student council activities may not be reported upon extensively unless they are particularly innovative or experimental. This could be interpreted as suggesting a lack of recognition as a result of institutionalisation. In practice, however, this very routinisation of regular meetings and discussion of general issues, may be the most effective way of ensuring students’ opinions are considered in the decision-making of the school. At the next stage of our work, we will need to pay particular attention to where youth voice (usually in the form of youth or student councils) is a statutory duty within both educational and local authority settings and how this empowers, or constrains, good practice.

Perhaps most starkly, we encountered national differences when considering the **critical dimensions of intersectionality and deliberation**. For example, our initial finding of relatively weak evidence of deliberative engagement in either community organisations or schools, opened up discussion about the way in which radical democratic discourse around ‘deliberation’ and movement beyond consensus-seeking takes place somewhat in parallel to more youth-oriented discourse on ‘voice’. While these criteria of ‘critique’ were included in the analysis in order to ensure these dimensions were not lost, it may be that they appeared to inherently prioritise an empowerment approach and deprioritise more traditional (Habermasian) modes of ‘deliberation’ rooted in ‘discussion’, ‘agreement’ and decision-making’. In building towards an assessment framework, therefore, it is essential to allow for the national and cultural context, the ‘tradition’ that pertains in any national or regional context, to be acknowledged

and built on. It also suggests the need for recommendations and programmes for youth organisations and schools to be clear about how the development of critical skills relates to other forms of communicative, deliberative and democratic practice.

This raises a related, but different, set of issues about different **modes** of delivery of youth participatory and deliberative activities. As outlined in Section 2.3, the cases selected for this study included a wide range of different types of organisations including: non-profit community organisations, charities or social enterprises; youth voice projects or services delivered by, or directly funded by, local councils or municipal authorities; umbrella or national youth organisations; individual schools (including independent, fee-paying schools) or educational trusts; and projects implemented across a number of schools funded by national or local government or international organisations. It follows that they were engaged in very different types of provision ranging from one-off ‘flagship’ projects to long-established youth or student councils that functioned as part of the everyday school, organisation or local authority governance structure. How to measure the relative contribution of such different forms of youth participation is a challenge. While flagship projects – around green initiatives, inclusion, no-tolerance to discrimination or bullying etc. – are engaging, mobilising and offer opportunities for genuine participation, they are delimited in terms of time frame and achievable goals and often delivered by external facilitators with fixed additional resources. In this way, they run the risk of becoming short time bubbles for a few young people and never being implemented for the good of the majority (Bruselius-Jenson and Nielsen, 2021). In reflecting on the potential framework for the Inclusivity Footprint Calculator, therefore, thought must be given to how to reflect the different contributions made by both short-term and long-term youth voice action programmes.

On this point, we must also not lose sight of the fact that resources matter. Project-based initiatives are attractive often because they come with dedicated, short-term, funding from external sources. Similarly, exceptionally strong practices identified may be built on funding from charitable foundations or independent (fee-paying) school status that cannot be replicated in other contexts. Recommended practices cannot be universal or assume high levels of material resources.

Finally, there can be no ‘one size fits all’ approach to the aims of youth voice programmes. This became evident in our study through a degree of tension between success in promoting ‘internal’ and ‘external’ efficacy in youth voice practices. For example, some programmes are excellent in delivering skills and education around participation in democratic practice such as voting, debating and deliberative democracy, designed to increase young people’s confidence in their abilities to participate but having more limited tangible impact on actual decision-making (and thus not building a sense of external efficacy among participants). Often such programmes are delivered by ‘experts’ or adult professionals with the agenda set by them rather than young people themselves and are thus underpinned by an understanding of young people as *citizens-in-the-making*, rather than equal, fully-fledged citizens. On the other hand, youth voice structures run by local or regional authorities were often able to demonstrate direct impact on local policy or organisational or school governance, providing a real sense of external efficacy but could be criticised for focusing on how young people’s voice can be used to ensure services are run more efficiently or for failing to adequately recognise the contribution of young people, or even

serving to co-opt or control, rather than empower, young people. Recognising these tensions might help us think about whether all programmes can, or should, deliver on all the elements of youth voice or whether integrated programmes of longer term, institutionalised structures need to go hand in hand with time-limited, project-based initiatives with more specific objectives. Equally, it might make us alert to tensions between theory and practice. While counterposing notions of ‘becoming’ and ‘being’ citizens might expose the discursive construction of youth, in practice we might need a more complex, dynamic and situated notion of youth citizenship as lying at the intersection of youth becoming, being and doing (Wood, 2022: 8-9).

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7. APPENDIX: RADAR ANALYSIS DIAGRAMS

This appendix provides a visualisation of the findings for each case analysed in this study. The points of the radar refer to the sub-criteria for coding listed against the main criteria – Inclusion (1), Participation (2), Deliberation (3), Intersectionality (4), Recognition (5) and Influence (6). Where the compact nature of the visualisation does not allow the full title of the sub-criterion to be displayed, please see Table 1 for the full list of the criteria and what they measured. The diagram indicates whether the case was coded at ‘1’, ‘0’ or ‘-1’ on each sub-criterion, as per the coding guidelines in Table 2. These diagrams should not be interpreted as an evaluation of the organisations or schools; the coding was designed simply to allow the generation of an overview of patterns in the demonstration of the different criteria across the two sites (schools vs organisations) and between countries.

Denmark Community Organisations

DFUU, DK

WDD, DK

RAP, DK

DUC, DK

TT, DK

UD, DK

AID, DK

Denmark Schools

FBHS, DK

H&RS, DK

MST, DK

EE, DK

FHS, DK

Finland Community Organisations

KYC, FI

LP, FI

SYC, FI

TYC, FI

YCV, FI

YCP, FI

CM, FI

GG, FI

HYI, FI

YP, FI

Finland Schools

Italy Community Organisations

ABC, IT

ID, IT

LQ, IT

CL, IT

Italy Schools

Portugal Community Organisations

Portugal Schools

United Kingdom Community Organisations

WVC, UK

SC, UK

WC, UK

LCC, UK

United Kingdom Schools

